

Disclosure under Noisy Information Processing

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Abstract

We study voluntary disclosure when investors observe firm reports through noisy information intermediaries such as auditors, analysts, rating agencies, or data providers. Any processing noise overturns the standard prediction of a unique partial-disclosure equilibrium. With low disclosure costs, the model unravels to full disclosure despite positive costs. With higher costs, the game admits two threshold equilibria featuring different disclosure probabilities. We characterize how the cost threshold for unraveling and the equilibrium set respond to changes in noise and fundamental uncertainty. In settings with high disclosure, both uncertainty and processing noise reduce disclosure, while higher certification costs can counterintuitively increase it. Endogenizing disclosure costs as optimal fees shows how profit-maximizing intermediaries select among equilibria, potentially generating a high-fee, high-disclosure regime. Extensions with bounded support, uncertain information endowment, endogenous noise, and competing information sources apply the insights to general information environments. The results caution against interpreting greater frictions as necessarily reducing disclosure.

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1 Introduction

In practice, most of the information flowing between managers, auditors, and investors is imperfect, incomplete, and open to some degree of interpretation. Forecasts, management commentary, and even disclosures during earnings forecasts are imprecise or selectively framed, and verification, through audits, due diligence, or external assurance, is costly. As a result, users of accounting information must decide how much to trust management claims, while preparers anticipate the market responses that their messages will attract. These frictions suggest that the processing of information by external parties is a noisy signal of the information voluntarily reported by the firm. Our study aims to develop a model that captures the tension between strategic communication and processing frictions, when users imperfectly process information.

The model features a noisy communication, in which the manager can issue a verified message at a cost but, at the time of disclosure does not fully know how users will process it. The environment introduces two-sided uncertainty: firms form expectations about investor reactions, while investors may discount overly optimistic messages as potentially noisy or biased. In doing so, we relax the standard assumption that disclosures are both truthful and perfectly received by users. Specifically, we examine whether noise dampens market responses to disclosed information, weakens firms' strategic incentives to disclose, and influences the equilibrium pricing of certification mechanisms, such as audits, credit ratings, or equity research reports.

Contrary to conventional models (Beyer et al. 2010; Stocken 2013), real-world disclosure practices suggest that information is rarely processed in a perfectly “noiseless” manner. Many firms report substantial uncertainty about how the market will interpret or react to their disclosures. While earnings announcements often convey quantitative metrics, such as earnings or revenue, voluntary disclosures about business models, strategies, and risks introduce a higher degree of complexity. These qualitative narratives are often as important as, if not more important than, the quantitative information itself. The result is a state of information overload, where, in the words of the former SEC Chair Mary Jo White, “*ever-increasing amounts of disclosure make it difficult for an investor to wade through the volume of information she receives to ferret out the information*”

that is most relevant.” Given the existence of partial processing, it is highly unlikely that firms can anticipate precisely which elements of their communications investors will successfully process or emphasize.

Numerous examples suggest that the processing of corporate information is inherently noisy. Companies frequently acknowledge that they cannot fully anticipate market reactions to their disclosures, explicitly noting this uncertainty in mandatory filings. For instance, in its July 28, 2009, in Amendment No. 4 to Form S-1 regarding the acquisition of eRx, Emdeon states: “*We cannot predict how investors will react when we file these financial statements or what effect it will have on the market price.*” Likewise, Apple in its 2023 Form 10-K states: “*The price of the Company’s stock is subject to volatility.[...] If the Company fails to meet expectations related to future growth, profitability, dividends, share repurchases or other market expectations, the price of the Company’s stock may decline significantly, which could have a material adverse impact on investor confidence and employee retention.*” and Novanta, in Form 10-K for the year ended December 31, 2023 explains that “*New products may also not be commercially successful as we cannot predict how the market will react to new products introduced by us or to enhancements made to our existing products.*”¹

Many institutional features of financial reporting illustrate the interaction between uncertainty and strategic disclosure. While our objective is not to model each institutional setting in detail, but rather to extract a common economic intuition, several applications demonstrate how the trade-off developed in our framework applies across diverse contexts. First, there are inherent limits to audit and assurance. Because auditors typically rely on sampling and may lack deep business-

¹These are three among many other examples: Hertz Global Holdings (“*We cannot predict how investors will react to the filing of our delayed financial statements or to our restatement,*” Form 10-K/A, 2015); Luckin Coffee Inc. (“*We cannot predict how investors will react to this restatement or what impact it may have on our ADSs,*” Form 20-F/A, 2020); Dell Technologies Inc. (“*We cannot predict how investors will react to the changes in our reporting structure or to the reclassification of prior periods,*” Form 10-K, 2021); Nikola Corp. (“*We cannot predict how investors will react to our delayed filings or the completion of our internal review,*” Form 10-K/A, 2021); Rite Aid Corp. (“*We cannot predict how investors will react to the filing of our restated financial statements or what effect it will have on the trading price of our common stock,*” Form 10-K/A, 2019); Bed Bath & Beyond Inc. (“*We cannot predict how investors will react to our disclosures regarding our liquidity and financing plans,*” Form 10-K, 2022); FTX Trading Ltd. (“*We cannot predict how creditors, investors, or regulators will respond to the release of restated financial information,*” provisional statement, 2023); and WeWork Inc. (“*We cannot predict how investors will react to the company’s revised financial disclosures or whether confidence will be restored,*” Form 8-K, 2023).

specific expertise, the information content of an audit is itself uncertain (Kachelmeier et al. 2020; Laux and Newman 2010). Moreover, auditors price their services strategically, incorporating this uncertainty into the valuation of assurance (Friedman and Mahieux 2021). Second, firms frequently disclose non-GAAP measures, which are less standardized and often less credible than audited financial information (Frankel et al. 2011; Doyle et al. 2013). These metrics require additional interpretation and processing by investors, increasing uncertainty about market reactions. Third, managers strategically adjust the tone, emphasis, and timing of disclosures, particularly when external verification is costly or limited (Jiang et al. 2019; Frankel et al. 2022). Finally, certain categories of disclosure, such as environmental or social impact reporting, are especially difficult to translate into firm value. In these cases, investors' responses may depend on personal preferences for non-financial outcomes (Friedman and Heinle 2016; Friedman et al. 2024; Sall 2025). Across all these contexts, three common assumptions are captured in our model: (i) managers exercise some discretion over what and how to disclose; (ii) they cannot perfectly anticipate market reactions; and (iii) there are preparation and verification costs, potentially paid to an external party, that determine the information available.

We show that even a small amount of noisy information processing can dramatically alter the standard insights on voluntary disclosure. In the canonical model of voluntary disclosure with no processing noise, there exists a unique equilibrium characterized by partial disclosure. Remarkably, this result need not hold once processing noise is introduced. To begin with, when verification costs are small *but positive*, the model unravels to full disclosure. The presence of processing noise induces marginal firms to disclose more; this allows lower types to mimic higher disclosing types more effectively, an incentive that will outweigh small verification costs. Furthermore, any partial-disclosure equilibrium is (generically) not unique. As verification costs rise beyond the threshold at which unravelling occurs, the model admits two distinct equilibria that feature different levels of disclosure. Even more strikingly, the equilibrium with more communication may involve more disclosure as costs increase. In the limit, full disclosure may emerge even for arbitrarily high verification costs. These properties imply that the presumption that frictions necessarily reduce

disclosure, may fail to hold within an otherwise standard model of voluntary disclosure.

The intuition behind this somewhat surprising result is that the common heuristic that higher costs reduce incentives to disclose, is inconsistent with the game-theoretic logic underlying disclosure equilibria. A disclosure game is not a single-agent decision problem in which the firm simply reduces information supply when disclosure becomes more costly (i.e., as if the firm reduced its consumption of a more expensive verification “good,” until its marginal utility equated the cost). Rather, as in the classic market for lemons, market prices endogenously adjust to the implied adverse selection, so that the demand for information, and thus the equilibrium disclosure incentive, will not remain constant when costs change. Indeed, in an equilibrium when verification costs are higher, the benefits of disclosure must also be higher, by construction, to justify incurring the cost. In the standard noiseless model, the marginal type’s net benefit from disclosure relative to non-disclosure increases monotonically with the threshold, implying that the equilibrium threshold rises with cost. However, this insight is fragile and does not hold once noise in information processing is introduced.

With noisy information processing, the benefit of disclosure becomes large over low disclosure thresholds such that disclosures are frequent. This arises because the marginal discloser is pooled with more favorable information, whereas withholding disclosure would reveal it to belong to the lower tail of the distribution. As a result, an increase in the verification cost must be offset by a corresponding increase in the net benefit of disclosure. This adjustment requires the disclosure threshold to decrease, leading to even more disclosure for the benefit to equate the cost. Consequently, the presence of processing noise fundamentally alters disclosure incentives, overturning the conventional view that higher costs necessarily reduce disclosure.

Ultimately, whether these effects arise depends on which equilibrium, frequent or infrequent disclosures, is being played. This is an empirical question that can only be resolved through observation of firms’ behavior, since in highly decentralized environments equilibrium selection may not be easily determined by theoretical criteria alone. In settings characterized by low overall disclosure, or where firms can coordinate on less informative prices or equilibria with low

verification costs, the model is consistent with standard comparative statics: the probability of disclosure decreases with higher costs, increases with greater signal precision, and rises when firms are better informed. By contrast, in environments with high baseline levels of disclosure, or where disclosure decisions are primarily shaped by investor demand for information, as is likely in modern financial markets, the opposite pattern may emerge. In these settings, higher costs may induce more disclosure, while noisier or less informative signals may be disclosed less frequently. In particular, the model suggests that the direction of comparative statics in disclosure behavior depends on the prevailing level of communication in the market.

We explore, in various extensions, closely related information environments. To begin with, we show that our main insights are robust to bounded maximum value losses (or deviations from normality) or when the firm has access to alternate information sources. In the latter case, preliminary results suggest that competition between multiple intermediaries may increase disclosure costs and reduce disclosure. We also show that, when it privately controls processing noise, the firm will ex-ante prefer a noisy system but this may, perhaps counter-intuitively, place it in a situation where third-parties charge a high cost for uninformative certifications. Finally, we show that, under pure uncertainty about information endowment, the equilibrium is unique and features a positive relationship between disclosure and noise, offering further scope to separate theories.

Our approach connects to several strands of the literature that share a focus on verified communication.² Within this literature, Suijs (2007) is most closely related to our work, as it analyzes a setting in which the sender cannot anticipate the receiver's reaction. However, his framework and underlying mechanism differ substantially from ours. In his model, even in the absence of frictions that prevent full unraveling, the sender may optimally withhold certain information because investors' allocation decisions are a non-linear function of disclosure. By not disclosing, the sender can hedge against adverse investor responses. In contrast, our model does not contain this

²This body of work has examined, for instance, the dynamic revelation of evidence (Guttman et al., 2014; Aghamolla and An, 2021; Kremer et al., 2024), the presence of alternative information channels (Einhorn, 2018; Frenkel et al., 2020; Lichtig and Weksler, 2023), and the interaction between disclosure and investment (Ben-Porath et al., 2018; Guttman and Meng, 2021). We differ from these studies by focusing specifically on processing noise and its implications for strategic disclosure and market pricing.

mechanism: the firm evaluates the average posterior belief, and the key friction arises because the investors observe the disclosure with noise. Thus, while both frameworks incorporate uncertainty about market responses, the mechanisms generate distinct equilibrium outcomes.

A second closely related study is Marinovic and Sridhar (2015), who, similar to our model, consider a third party producing a noisy signal equal to the disclosed information plus an additive noise term, and also analyze the pricing incentives of that intermediary. We build on their approach. However, their entire analysis relies on an approximation (Assumption 2, p. 33) that treats the firm's expectation over the noise as interchangeable with a non-linear pricing function.³ Further, while they explicitly note that the approximation is invalid for non-arbitrarily large noise, we show that statements obtained under this approximation do not hold even close to limits of the model, e.g., among other examples, unravelling equilibria can exist, the existence of a unique partial-disclosure equilibrium is non-generic, and the comparative statics in the set of equilibria do not match those with the approximation.

Several other studies consider the value of certification, from the perspective of interactions between voluntary and mandatory channels. Jiang and Yang (2017) and Bertomeu et al. (2021) show that a mandatory disclosure of bad news, as in conservative accounting systems, can reduce the equilibrium signalling costs incurred voluntarily to credibly communicate good news. Other studies such as Versano (2021) and Jiang et al. (2023) describe environments in which voluntary choices to certify can provide information above and beyond a disclosure mandate. While we also focus on certification, the intuitions from these previously-documented mechanisms would also hold in our setting, so, to better focus on the main new point of our study, we focus here primarily on voluntary channels.

Two additional strands of the disclosure literature also relate to our analysis. The first examines strategic disclosure when information arrives after the sender's disclosure decision. The earliest

³It is possible that this approximation could be valid in the case of infinite noise, but the problem is that the approximation is based on a Taylor expansion (which is valid at a single point) that is applied as a functional approximation for all signal values on the real line. As a result, the link between infinite noise and finite noise need not be maintained, because the quality of the pointwise Taylor expansion declines in the upper and lower tails. Furthermore, the approximation is only argued to be valid for large noise, while, in many real-world applications, we would be interested in noise that is small or moderate (or, at least, not arbitrarily large).

contribution in this area is Einhorn (2018), followed by subsequent studies exploring how the timing and characteristics of external information affect disclosure incentives. For example, Libgober et al. (2023) analyze a setting in which the receiver’s signal may be garbled, while Frenkel et al. (2020) study a case where an analyst can infer private information when the sender is informed. As in our model, the sender is uncertain about the receiver’s beliefs, which shapes disclosure incentives. However, these studies focus on the effects of external (third-party) signals conditional on non-disclosure, whereas in our framework, miscommunication arises from the garbling of the sender’s own message.

Another related strand highlights the role of mixed strategies in disclosure equilibria, where a true signal is combined to garbling noise via a mixture. Marinovic (2013) considers a setting in which the receiver is uncertain whether the sender is truthful or strategic, leading the latter to mix messages to imitate a truthful sender’s distribution. Similarly, Frenkel et al. (2024) analyze an environment with a noisy or unreliable information source, such as “fake news,” and show that a pure-strategy equilibrium fails to exist. While the contexts differ, the intuition for equilibrium mixing parallels our model. A firm with a signal above a conjectured disclosure threshold expects more favorable news on average and thus anticipates a highly positive market reaction when it withholds disclosure.

2 The Model

We describe below a model in which, first, a certifier, e.g., a rating agency, a broker assisting an equity issue, or an auditor, sets a fee and, second, a privately informed firm decides whether to make a certified disclosure. Hereafter, we refer to this action as “disclosure” or “certification” to describe a costly action to provide public verifiable information. To make the intuitions as clear-cut as possible, we assume, admittedly without intent for realism, that the firm has no other means to credibly disclose its information. The quality of the public disclosure is exogenously given but, throughout, is only a noisy signal of what the firm actually observes. This assumption separates our results from the primary trade-off analyzed in Lizzeri (1999) and Marinovic and Sridhar (2015),

where decreasing the quality of the information may increase disclosure. However, in comparative statics, we shall demonstrate that such a monotone comparative statics in the noise is not always true in our setting.

Formally, the sequence of events starts with the certifier committing to a fee c . The firm privately observes its realized value, denoted $\tilde{v} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ with mean normalized to zero. Note that we mean that the firm has an information set that is strictly more precise than the certifier, as it may be that \tilde{v} is itself a noisy estimate of future cash flows. Alternatively, one may interpret the disclosure problem more abstractly as releasing information that is observed only with noise by investors or such that $\tilde{v} = \tilde{v}_1 + \tilde{v}_2$ but investors only process one of the components. For example, consistent with this interpretation, the firm is unlikely to convey all of its information in its financial statements or perfectly know the market response to its disclosure (Suijs 2007; Einhorn 2007). Importantly, our main results will continue to hold even if the noise were small, as we show that *any* noise will fundamentally affect the nature of the equilibrium set.

The firm can incur the cost c , in which case the certifier publicly issues a signal $\tilde{x} = \tilde{v} + \tilde{\varepsilon}$, where $\tilde{\varepsilon} \sim N(0, s^2)$ is normally-distributed white noise. The assumption captures that the certifier will typically know less than the firm and, even if the firm were to attempt to communicate its information or share current transactions, not all relevant facts about future cash flows may be verifiable. In other words, the noise is a technical short-hand to reflect inherent frictions impairing the flow of information. Otherwise, no disclosure is made, denoted by the symbol \emptyset . Importantly, while we use here the normal distribution because of its regularity, we show later on that the primary insights do not depend on the normal or a distribution whose support is unbounded.

The firm's objective is to maximize the expected price net of certification cost: for any realization of the firm value v ,

$$d(v) \in \arg \max_{d \in \{0,1\}} (d\mathbb{E}P(v + \tilde{\varepsilon}; c) + (1 - d)P(\emptyset; c) - dc), \quad (1)$$

such that the disclosure prices $P(\tilde{x}; c)$ and the no-disclosure price $P(\emptyset; c)$ are functions of the cost c . To reduce clutter, we occasionally omit the explicit dependence on c when solving only for the firm's optimal disclosure.

When possible (i.e., over non-zero probability events), the price $P(\cdot)$ must satisfy Bayes rule as the expectation of \tilde{v} conditional on the public information available to investors, that is, $P(x; c) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|d(\tilde{v}) = 1, x)$ and $P(\emptyset; c) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|d(\tilde{v}) = 0)$. We consider threshold “sanitization” equilibria, such that the firm certifies $d(v) = 1$ if and only if $v \geq \tau(c)$ (Shin 1994; Guttman et al. 2014).⁴

The firm’s optimal strategy can then be simplified to an indifference condition such that the marginal discloser (at the threshold) achieves an expected price

$$\mathbb{E}P(\tau(c) + \tilde{\varepsilon}; c) - c = P(\emptyset; c), \quad (2)$$

and the associated market prices are given by

$$P(x; c) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} \geq \tau(c), x), \quad P(\emptyset; c) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} < \tau(c)). \quad (3)$$

Finally, the certifier chooses the fee to maximize its profit,

$$c^* \in \arg \max_{c \leq \bar{c}} c(1 - \Phi(\tau(c)/\sigma)), \quad (4)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ (with pdf $\phi(\cdot)$) is the cdf of the standard normal.⁵ The sequence of events is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Model timeline

Definition 1. For a given fee c , a subgame equilibrium is a price function $P(\cdot; c)$ and a threshold $\tau(c)$, with values in $\overline{\mathbb{R}}$, such that:

- (i) the equilibrium conditions (2)-(3) are satisfied;
- (ii) if $\tau(c) = -\infty$ (resp., $\tau(c) = \infty$) involves either full disclosure (resp., no-disclosure) almost

⁴That the equilibrium is a threshold is a consequence of the monotone likelihood ratio property (MLRP), since MLRP is preserved by truncation. That is, $P(x; c) = \mathbb{E}(v|v \in A, x)$ is increasing in x for a non-zero probability non-disclosure set A , so that the expected disclosure price $\mathbb{E}(P(v + \tilde{\varepsilon}; c)|v, A)$ must also be increasing in v . A formal proof is given in a companion supplementary appendix.

⁵The upper bound \bar{c} is not critical for our analysis and is made to avoid an extreme situation in which firms might make arbitrarily negative surplus. For example, one may interpret \bar{c} in terms of the maximal ex-ante benefit from becoming public (excluding disclosure costs) via, say, greater access to capital markets. If c were too large, firms would prefer to stay private and managers would thus no longer make any public disclosures.

surely, then the threshold firm would also prefer this choice at any finite threshold.⁶

In the benchmark where the noise s is exactly zero (that is, setting $\mathbb{E}(P(\tilde{x}; c)|v) = v$), the firm's problem simplifies to costly disclosure. From the property that the normal distribution is log-concave with sub-exponential tails, Verrecchia (1983) shows that for any $c > 0$, there is a unique interior threshold $\tau(c) \in \mathbb{R}$.

With noise, however, there will be situations in which there is no partial-disclosure equilibrium despite a positive cost; therefore, the solution concept must be adapted to explicitly describe such outcome. One issue is that, by imposing (i) only, full disclosure with $\tau(c) = P(\emptyset; c) = -\infty$ will always be an equilibrium. To address this, condition (ii) requires full disclosure to occur only if it can be rationalized as a strict incentive to certify for *any* conjectured threshold. This guarantees that unravelling is a natural implication of the model (i.e., starting from any conjectured threshold, firms prefer more certification) rather than being artificially engineered from unbounded skeptical off-equilibrium beliefs.⁷

Definition 2. A certification (subgame-perfect) equilibrium is given by a certification fee c^* , such that (i) c^* maximizes the certifier profit in (4) and (ii) for any fee $c \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $(P(\cdot; c), \tau(c))$ is a subgame equilibrium as given in Definition 1.

We solve the model by backward induction. First, we characterize the firm's optimal disclosure for any possible fee c . After the fee is observed, the problem faced by the firm is a proper subgame of the main game that can be described as a costly disclosure model. Second, we examine the optimal choice of the certifier, considering how the choice of fees may lead to different profits in the subgame. In the next section, we examine properties of the subgame for a given c and, to simplify the exposition, do not explicitly write the dependence of prices on c .

⁶Formally: for any $\hat{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}$ and price $\hat{P}(x) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} \geq \hat{\tau}, x)$, $\Delta(\hat{\tau}) = \mathbb{E}\hat{P}(\hat{\tau} + \tilde{\varepsilon}; c) - c - \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} < \hat{\tau})$ is positive if $\tau(c) = -\infty$ and negative if $\tau(c) = \infty$.

⁷Symmetrically, we rule out no-disclosure caused by punishing expectations $P(x; c) = -\infty$ after any disclosure, say, if investors were to expect that only unboundedly unfavorable signals were disclosed.

3 Optimal Disclosure

3.1 Prices under Noisy Disclosure

Unlike traditional disclosure frameworks à la Verrecchia (1983) and Dye (1985), investors in the model never directly observe the firm's private information, even when a disclosure occurs. Instead, they form a Bayesian inference $P(x)$ based on their conjectured disclosure strategy, using the observed message x to extract information about the true firm value v .

First, the marginal discloser $v = \tau(c)$ is, by construction, the firm with the lowest value among those choosing to disclose. Observing a disclosure therefore reveals that $\tilde{v} \geq \tau(c)$, prompting a positive revision in investors' posterior beliefs. However, because the signal is noisy, investors cannot fully disentangle the marginal type from higher types and thus tend to update beliefs too optimistically. Second, higher-value firms that disclose are no longer precisely identified: if the disclosure threshold $\tau(c)$ is low, investors may respond with excessive skepticism, attributing high signals partly to noise rather than strong fundamentals. Consequently, the noise attenuates the price response to disclosure, flattening the mapping between disclosures and market valuations.

The first step of our analysis establishes a technical lemma that, using condition (ii) in Definition 1, rules out equilibria in which disclosure occurs only off the equilibrium path. Such equilibria are implausible because, in principle, a firm possessing sufficiently favorable private information should be willing to pay a finite certification fee, even when the signal is noisy.

Lemma 1. *There exists a subgame equilibrium, and any such equilibrium must be such that $\tau(c) < \infty$, i.e., cannot feature no-disclosure with probability one.*

Having shown that disclosure always occurs with positive probability, the market price conditional on observing a noisy signal x can be written explicitly as

$$P(x) = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{v}|x, \tilde{v} \geq \tau] = \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2}x + \frac{\sigma s}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \frac{\phi\left(\frac{\tau - \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2}x}{\frac{\sigma s}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}}}\right)}{1 - \Phi\left(\frac{\tau - \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2}x}{\frac{\sigma s}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}}}\right)}. \quad (5)$$

The right-hand side follows from standard properties of truncated normal distributions applied to the bivariate normal vector (\tilde{v}, \tilde{x}) ; see, for example, Horrace (2005). In the absence of disclosure, investors receive no additional information, so the price as a function of the disclosure threshold is

$$P(\emptyset) = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} < \tau] = -\sigma \frac{\phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})}{\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})}. \quad (6)$$

Note that the firm does not know the realization of the noise when it decides to disclose; hence, its net benefit from disclosure is obtained by taking expectations in (5) over all realizations of $\tilde{x} | v \sim N(v, s^2)$ given the privately-observed value v :

$$\mathbb{E}[P(\tilde{x}) | v] = \frac{1}{s} \int P(x) \phi\left(\frac{x-v}{s}\right) dx. \quad (7)$$

Given that the expression for $P(x)$ is cumbersome, and the integrand is not in closed form, it is convenient to write this equation in terms of the expectations of a transformed standard normal.

Lemma 2. *The expected price evaluated for the marginal discloser $v = \tau$ is*

$$\mathbb{E}(P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau) = a(s) \tau + b(s) \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta_s(\tilde{Y}))], \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{Y} \sim N(0, 1)$ is a standard normal random variable and

$$a(s) \equiv \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2}, \quad b(s) \equiv \frac{s\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}}, \quad \lambda(z) \equiv \frac{\phi(z)}{1 - \Phi(z)}, \quad \theta_s(\tilde{Y}) \equiv \frac{\tau s / \sigma - \sigma \tilde{Y}}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}}.$$

Further, $\partial \mathbb{E}(P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau) / \partial \tau \in (0, 1)$.

Lemma 2 will be useful in proving our main results but also offers critical intuition about how noise affects the payoff of the marginal discloser. The expected price in (8) consists of two components. The first component, weighted by $a(s) \in (0, 1)$, captures how a disclosure reflects the firm's private information. This term is linear in τ , implying that the expected payoff deteriorates uniformly as τ decreases, regardless of the threshold.

Without noise, the weight $a(s)$ equals one, so that the marginal effect of a decrease in the threshold on the firm's payoff remains exactly one. In comparison, from the log-concavity of the normal distribution (and many other "regular" distributions), $P(\emptyset)$ is an average of values below

the threshold, and thus decreases more slowly than one as τ falls. Consequently, the difference $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] - P(\emptyset)$ shrinks as τ decreases, leading to the well-known unique equilibrium in Verrecchia (1983).

With noise, however, equation (8) includes an additional term weighted by $b(s)$. This second component reflects the market's residual uncertainty: after a disclosure, investors know that $v \geq \tau$ but cannot determine with certainty the firm's private information. In the limit of infinite noise, for example, the equation simplifies to $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)] = \mathbb{E}(v | v \geq \tau)$, since the market can only infer that, on the equilibrium path, some type above τ made the disclosure. More generally, the expected price of the marginal discloser is also a weighted average of the potential disclosers with $v \geq \tau$. This averaging effect dampens the sensitivity of expected prices to changes in the threshold, so that the slope is now strictly less than one.

In turn, the net benefit of disclosure, $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)] - P(\emptyset)$, is no longer monotonic because the disclosure payoff is flattened by the weight $b(s)$. Intuitively, the slope of each component with respect to τ depends on the extent of averaging. When τ is large, $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)]$ is averaged over a smaller set of values $v \geq \tau$, whereas $P(\emptyset)$ is averaged over a larger set of values $v < \tau$. Consequently, the former term increases more steeply in τ . Conversely, when τ is small, the situation is reversed, and the net benefit of disclosure *increases* as τ becomes smaller. We establish this result formally in the next lemma.

Lemma 3. $\lim_{|\tau| \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)] - c - P(\emptyset) = \infty$.

Lemma 3 shows that the net benefit of disclosure remains strictly positive relative to non-disclosure for values of τ sufficiently close to full-disclosure ($\tau \rightarrow -\infty$).⁸ As a consequence, there is greater scope for equilibria in which unravelling coexists with positive disclosure costs, since disclosure introduces upside uncertainty: the market infers that the firm may be better than

⁸This property holds for any c (even large) due to the unbounded support of the normal distribution, though an analogous result can be established for other distributions with unbounded support. The insight is more general: if the support is bounded, the same conclusion applies over a range of positive c (whereas it would be zero in the absence of noise). Intuitively, when the distribution of firm values is bounded from below, any equilibrium in which the cost exceeds the mean value would imply non-disclosure with probability one. In practice, however, worst-case realizations of firm values are typically associated with economically large negative outcomes (e.g., bankruptcy, litigation, etc.) relative to the cost of certifying information.

the marginal type. In fact, if the difference $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)] - P(\emptyset)$ does not shrink sufficiently as τ increases, the only equilibrium in the subgame will unravel to full-disclosure, with even arbitrarily low-value firms choosing to pay a positive cost to disclose.

3.2 Equilibrium Disclosure

To gain intuition, Figure 2 plots an illustrative example in which the conjectured threshold τ is varied to characterize equilibria satisfying the indifference condition. The price $P(\emptyset)$ does not depend on the cost c or the noise level s , and is a concave function that increases at a rate less than one from $-\infty$ to the unconditional mean $\mathbb{E}(v) = 0$. The marginal discloser payoff $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)] - c$ is an average of a mirror-image upper truncation $v \geq \tau$: it is convex with a slope converging to one as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$. An increase in the cost c can then be represented as a uniform downward shift of the net benefit from disclosure.

Starting from a sufficiently low cost $c \approx 1$, the two curves do not intersect: the net benefit of disclosure remains strictly above the non-disclosure price. Intuitively, the marginal discloser always strictly benefits from revealing information by pooling over $v \geq \tau$, and this benefits exceeds the disclosure cost. Note also that this unravelling outcome does not require quantitatively extreme assumptions about the economic primitives; it is the unique equilibrium when costs and noise are set equal to a standard-deviation of the fundamental uncertainty.

Figure 2: Expected disclosure net of costs $\mathbb{E}[P(x)] - c$ in blue and $P(\emptyset)$ for different thresholds, with equilibrium indicated as a circle ($\sigma = s = 1$).

As the cost increases, the disclosure-benefit curve shifts downward until it becomes tangent to $P(\emptyset)$, at which point the benefit from disclosure exactly offsets the cost. Beyond this critical value, the two curves intersect twice, giving rise to two subgame equilibria. The equilibrium with the lower threshold features more frequent disclosure (and more informative prices) but more skeptical beliefs conditional on non-disclosure. By contrast, the equilibrium with the higher threshold is such that less information is disclosed. This threshold is typically preferred by firms, since they obtain a higher price when not disclosing and are pooled with better types when they disclose.

Our next proposition establishes, by formally proving the convexity of $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) \mid \tau]$ together with the concavity of $P(\emptyset)$, that, generically, there exists either a unique subgame equilibrium featuring unravelling or two subgame equilibria corresponding to distinct disclosure levels, for *any* level of noise.

Proposition 1. *There is a cost level $c_0 > 0$ such that:*

- (i) *if $c < c_0$, the unique subgame equilibrium is full disclosure, with threshold $\tau(c) = -\infty$;*
- (ii) *if $c = c_0$, the unique subgame equilibrium features partial disclosure threshold $\tau(c_0) < 0$;*
- (iii) *if $c > c_0$, the game admits exactly two subgame equilibria. These are characterized by finite thresholds $\underline{\tau}(c)$ and $\bar{\tau}(c)$, continuous in c . As c increases from c_0 to ∞ , the lower threshold $\underline{\tau}(c)$ falls from $\tau(c_0)$ to $-\infty$, while the upper threshold $\bar{\tau}(c)$ rises from $\tau(c_0)$ to ∞ .*

Proposition 1 contrasts sharply with the classical noiseless benchmark of Verrecchia (1983), in which the equilibrium exhibits partial disclosure for every positive disclosure cost. By contrast, we show that once information processing is noisy, full disclosure can arise for a range of strictly positive costs. Moreover, the game generically admits two partial-disclosure equilibria for higher costs, one of which features more disclosure as the cost increases.

At first glance, one might expect a higher disclosure cost to *necessarily* reduce the probability of disclosure, since a higher cost lowers the net benefit of revealing information. However, as shown in Figure 3, this intuition need not hold: the effect depends on the degree of market skepticism. Although this result may appear counterintuitive, it is in fact the “cost” intuition itself that can be misleading, as we explain below.

Figure 3: The two equilibrium thresholds $\underline{\tau}(c)$ and $\bar{\tau}(c)$ vary with c ($\sigma = s = 1$).

Figure 4: Maximum cost c_0 consistent with full-disclosure.

Analogous to the classic market for lemons (Akerlof 1970), the firm faces investors adjusting their beliefs to correct for adverse selection. Consequently, the demand for a verified disclosure need not slope downward in the cost if investors anticipate more severe adverse selection. Absent any disclosure noise ($s = 0$), the net benefit of disclosure $\tau - P(\emptyset)$ is strictly increasing in the threshold. Hence, adverse selection and the probability of disclosure cannot simultaneously increase.

With noisy disclosure, on the other hand, the net benefit of disclosure is non-monotonic. At the upper threshold $\bar{\tau}(c)$, where the probability of disclosure is low, disclosures tend to be more precise because investors already know that $v \geq \bar{\tau}(c)$. This corresponds to the conventional comparative static in which higher costs lead to less disclosure. At the lower threshold $\underline{\tau}(c)$, however, when markets are skeptical to non-disclosure, greater disclosure raises the net benefit of disclosing: it becomes harder to distinguish marginal disclosers with $v \geq \underline{\tau}(c)$, while non-disclosure becomes more revealing. Higher costs therefore call for a higher net benefit of disclosure, driving the equilibrium threshold further into the lower tail. Strikingly, the probability of disclosure will *increase* with the cost of disclosure. Indeed, in the limit as $c \rightarrow \infty$, firms unravel to full-disclosure with an arbitrarily costly disclosure.

The duality of subgame equilibria arises from a fundamental trade-off: whether the gap between disclosure and non-disclosure stems from more precise disclosure at $\bar{\tau}(c)$ or from more precise non-disclosure at $\underline{\tau}(c)$. Given a higher cost, this gap must increase to balance the cost.

When the threshold is expected to be high, i.e., in environments with low levels of disclosure,

disclosure events “ $v \geq \tau$ ” tend to more precisely indicate good news, so that a higher threshold tends to increase the post-disclosure expectation more sharply. The higher cost must be balanced with an increase in the post-disclosure expectation, leading to a higher disclosure threshold (and a lower probability of disclosure). By contrast, when investors expect the threshold to be low, i.e., disclosure levels are low, a disclosure conveys less information than a non-disclosure “ $\tilde{v} < \tau$.” For a higher cost, the gap must then be increased by making the non-disclosure more precise, which is achieved by further decreasing τ , increasing the probability of disclosure.

Joining both intuitions, the firm is not reducing its consumption of “certified disclosure” as in a standard demand model, because its benefit to disclose is not exogenously decreasing in their conjecture level of disclosure. Instead, this benefit is determined by the informational value of the disclosed signal. It is a non-monotonic function of the disclosure threshold, highest in the lower and upper tails when either a disclosure or non-disclosure best separates extreme signals.

It is worth noting that this fundamental force behind the seemingly counterintuitive comparative statics does not rely on unbounded support of firm value. Unboundedness matters only for tail behavior: it allows the lower threshold to keep shifting down as the cost increases, because non-disclosure can be made arbitrarily punitive. With bounded support, the same mechanism operates over an intermediate cost range. However, once the threshold approaches the lower bound of the support, no disclosure becomes the unique equilibrium. We discuss this in detail in Section 5.1.

At this stage, we remain agnostic about which equilibrium will prevail. Nevertheless, a few remarks are warranted to address whether coordination on a particular equilibrium would be straightforward in a large decentralized capital market. In a rational expectations framework, firms do not choose which equilibrium to play: their actions are instead determined by expectations over price formation. Moreover, decentralized capital markets consist of many firms with no obvious means of communication or pre-commitment to reduce disclosure costs. Unlike small-group or team-based settings, where participants might coordinate to achieve efficiency or apply game-theoretic refinements, high levels of coordination may be less plausible in large, decentralized environments involving numerous firms and investors.

Naturally, the multiplicity of equilibria is not unique to our setting and is a common feature of many communication games, including cheap talk (Crawford and Sobel 1982; Fischer and Stocken 2001; Morgan and Stocken 2003), signalling (Guttman et al. 2006), standard-setting (Chen and Yang 2023), and even verifiable disclosure models (Aghamolla and Smith 2023). Such multiplicity cannot always be reduced through refinements or by appealing to straightforward institutional features. Philosophically, multiplicity, and its implied indeterminacy (or “sunspots”), may be an intrinsic property of certain environments rather than an incompleteness in our theoretical understanding that must be assumed away (Dybvig 2023).⁹

In our model, the two subgame equilibria exhibit distinct properties that can be more or less appealing depending on features of the empirical setting. On the one hand, the lower threshold $\underline{\tau}(c)$ maximizes the information available to investors and would be “receiver-preferred” when the problem is framed as a sender–receiver game in which investors make additional real decisions. Truth-leaning equilibria (Hart et al. 2017; Rappoport forthcoming) tend to select more communication, and the common emphasis on fully revealing equilibria in signalling games, or on the most informative equilibria in cheap-talk models (Fischer and Stocken 2001; Chen et al. 2008), implicitly assumes that communications gravitate toward more communication, even when equilibria less costly to the sender, such as pooling or babbling, exist.

On the other hand, the upper threshold $\bar{\tau}(c)$ is preferred by firms, as lower investor skepticism enables them to disclose less while still achieving higher prices. Firms would attain this equilibrium if they could credibly communicate neologisms to investors (Bertomeu and Cianciaruso 2018), which ultimately depends on their ability to be heard and to influence market expectations. This

⁹A notable exception is provided by global games, which were specifically designed to capture coordination failures in large decentralized interactions; see, e.g., Stocken and Zhang (2025) for an application in financial reporting. To our knowledge, however, informational perturbations of the kind used in global games do not restrict equilibria in disclosure settings. Still, as in global games, it is natural to assume that some players may fail to coordinate on their preferred equilibrium. Furthermore, there are environments in which no single refinement criterion dominates all others. In cheap-talk models, for instance, the diversity of human languages and behaviors suggests that a unique refinement may not exist—an observation that parallels the historical evolution of accounting toward specific institutional rules and definitions (Zeff 1972; Waymire and Basu 2008). Even in the special case of large publicly-traded firms, it is not obvious that these firms could easily engage in explicit communication to coordinate market expectations to play an equilibrium with less disclosure, as this could be interpreted as market manipulation or may be viewed as exerting coordinated market power (on suppliers of information) possibly forbidden by antitrust authorities.

trade-off between the informativeness of communication and its strategic cost arises in other settings as well. Signalling models, for instance, can feature less informative (pooling) equilibria alongside lower signalling costs (see, e.g., Stocken and Verrecchia 2004; Guttman et al. 2006), as do models in the real-effects literature (Kanodia 2007).

3.3 Comparative Statics

Our next step is to examine the comparative statics of the maximal cost c_0 , below which firms' disclosures unravel to full-disclosure.

Corollary 1. *As the noise s or the fundamental uncertainty σ increases from 0 to ∞ , the unravelling bound c_0 increases, with $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} c_0 = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} c_0 = 0$.¹⁰ Further, $\tau(c_0) < 0$.*

The effect of the information environment in implementing a full-disclosure outcome is consistent with several earlier intuitions. We plot the bound c_0 as a function of (s, σ) in Figure 4.

The additional noise s flattens the marginal discloser's price, preventing investors from precisely identifying the marginal discloser; in turn, this increases the set of costs such that the net benefit of disclosure is strictly greater than the non-disclosure price. How a higher σ affects this trade-off further matches the intuition in Verrecchia (1990): there is more information transmitted in the disclosure (per unit of cost), also increasing the firm's disclosure propensity and nudging the model further toward full disclosure. Interestingly, the tangency point $\tau(c_0) < 0$ is below the unconditional mean, suggesting that the discontinuous jump to partial disclosure when c_0 is attained cannot be too large and must initially affect only unconditionally unfavorable information.

We turn next to the comparative statics in the noise s and the volatility of fundamentals σ . The comparative statics in σ requires more caution because the threshold is only a description of the strategy while the probability of disclosure is jointly affected by a shift in the threshold and a change in the distribution of fundamentals. To address this, we examine the probability of disclosure $Prob(v \geq \tau(c)) = 1 - \Phi(\tau(c)/\sigma)$, which is monotone in the threshold for a change in

¹⁰In a supplementary appendix, we also show that c_0 converges to a finite value when either σ or s becomes large.

noise s but otherwise requires a total derivative of the numerator and denominator of $\tau(c)/\sigma$.¹¹

Corollary 2. *Suppose that $c > c_0$, the probability of disclosure*

(i) increases in the noise s under $\bar{\tau}(c)$ and, under $\underline{\tau}(c)$, decreases in s ;

(ii) increases in the uncertainty σ under $\bar{\tau}(c) > 0$ and, under $\underline{\tau}(c)$, decreases for small σ .¹²

In addition, under $\underline{\tau}(c)$, the equilibrium converges to full-disclosure if s or σ converge to zero or σ becomes large.

We plot the comparative statics of the probability of disclosure with respect to the signal noise s and the volatility of the fundamental σ in Figure 5. More noise in disclosure increases the payoff to the marginal discloser by pooling it with a wider range of values $v \geq \tau(c)$. This increases the net benefit of disclosure which, all else equal, acts similar to a reduction in the disclosure cost. To remain consistent with equilibrium, this effect must be offset against a lower informational value of disclosure. Under the upper equilibrium $\bar{\tau}(c)$, this adjustment occurs through less precise disclosures, via a lower threshold and a higher probability of disclosure. Vice-versa, under the lower equilibrium $\underline{\tau}(c)$, the adjustment occurs from a less precise non-disclosure, which is achieved with a higher probability of non-disclosure. Surprisingly, even a small amount of noise can dramatically alter the predictions of the model: as $s \rightarrow 0$, the equilibrium under $\underline{\tau}(c)$ unravels to full-disclosure.

For similar reasons, the comparative statics with respect to fundamental uncertainty need not match the prediction in Verrecchia (1990), which states that, without noise, firms disclose more as σ increases. While this prediction holds in the upper equilibrium $\bar{\tau}(c)$, it becomes ambiguous under the lower equilibrium $\underline{\tau}(c)$. An increase in uncertainty has two opposing effects: it reduces the relative cost of disclosure but also diminishes the relative noise (per unit of uncertainty). These

¹¹It can be problematic to focus on comparative statics on the threshold $\tau(c)$, unless the threshold has a monotone mapping with the probability of disclosure. Consider the following example in Dye (1985) and Jung and Kwon (1988). Suppose that the measurement is changed from US dollars to Chinese yuans, at a rate of 1 for 7. It is clear that this unit of measurement should have no effects on any meaningful economics of the problem (and will not change the probability of disclosure), despite the fact that the actual threshold in yuans will be higher, at seven times the threshold in dollars. From an economic standpoint, the object of analysis is the final allocations, i.e., the probability of disclosure and distribution of prices, not properties of the threshold.

¹²The probability of disclosure under $\underline{\tau}(c)$ will either attain full-disclosure (if c is small) or, otherwise, strictly increase in σ when σ is large; however, this latter case, while we know that it can occur, implies for any parameter values a probability of disclosure that is very close to one (above .99).

with $c = 1.5$ and $\sigma = 1$

with $c = 1.5$ and $s = 1$

Figure 5: Comparative statics of $\Pr(\tilde{v} \geq \bar{\tau}(c))$.

mechanisms work in opposite directions, generating a non-monotonic effect on the probability of disclosure. In particular, the model unravels to full disclosure when uncertainty is either very high or very low. More generally, the probability of disclosure decreases with uncertainty in environments where uncertainty is low.

4 The Certifier's Problem

4.1 Certifier Profit Function

Having characterized the equilibria of the subgame, we are equipped to recover the optimal certification fee. To do so, we solve the full game by backward induction, moving next to the certifier's optimal choice of fee taking the subgame equilibrium as given and optimizing over the fee c to solve

$$V(c^*; \tau(c^*)) = \max_{c \leq \bar{c}} c(1 - \Phi(\frac{\tau(c)}{\sigma})), \quad (9)$$

where $\tau(c)$ is a threshold in the subgame. Note that, in (9), the certifier forms belief that $\tau(c)$ is a subgame equilibrium but does not directly choose it.

The certifier's profit is plotted in Figure 6, as a function of the chosen fee. As long as $c \leq c_0$, the subgame equilibrium is unique with a full-disclosure profit $V(c; -\infty) = c$ increasing when $c < c_0$ but falling (discontinuously) to $V(c_0; \tau(c_0)) = c_0(1 - \Phi(\frac{\tau(c_0)}{\sigma}))$ at the lowest fee $c = c_0$ compatible with an interior solution. In turn, this implies the following key observation in the certifier game: low fees $c \leq c_0$ cannot be a solution for the certifier's problem, as we explain below.

Figure 6: Certifier profit $V(c)$ ($\sigma = s = 1$).

To begin with, any fee $c < c_0$ within the full-disclosure region is such that $V(c; -\infty) = c$, increasing in the fee because (at these fee levels) all firms certify. As a result, if such a fee c were optimal, the profit could be further increased by increasing slightly toward c_0 , e.g., $c' = (c + c_0)/2$, contradicting the optimality of any choice $c < c_0$ and implying that c_0 is a lower bound on the equilibrium fee.

But $c = c_0$ cannot be an equilibrium either, because under our maintained assumption (ii) in Definition 1 that investors do not form (unboundedly) skeptical non-disclosure beliefs unless they prefer disclosure at any disclosure threshold, the interior equilibrium implies a discrete loss of revenue as $V(c_0; \tau(c_0)) = c_0(1 - \Phi(\frac{\tau(c_0)}{\sigma})) < c_0$. The consequence of this property is that some fee strictly below c_0 is always preferred by the certifier to c_0 , e.g., $c' = \frac{1}{2}(V(c_0; \tau(c_0)) + c_0)$, also contradicting the optimality of c_0 .

Then, a solution to the certifier's problem must be found at $c > c_0$. In what follows, define

$$\underline{V}(c) \equiv V(c; \underline{\tau}(c)) = c(1 - \Phi(\frac{\underline{\tau}(c)}{\sigma})), \quad \bar{V}(c) \equiv V(c; \bar{\tau}(c)) = c(1 - \Phi(\frac{\bar{\tau}(c)}{\sigma})), \quad (10)$$

with the convention that $\underline{V}(c) = \bar{V}(c) = V(c; \tau(c))$ when $c \leq c_0$.

Lemma 4. *If $c \geq c_0$, $\underline{V}(c)$ is increasing in c with $\lim_{c \rightarrow \infty} \underline{V}(c) = \infty$ and $\bar{V}(c)$ is decreasing in c when $\frac{c_0}{\sigma} \lambda\left(\frac{\bar{\tau}(c_0)}{\sigma}\right) > 1$. Further, $\lim_{c \rightarrow \infty} \bar{V}(c) = 0$.*

In Lemma 4, we show that the two thresholds have different implications for the certifier's strategy. When anticipating the more informative lower threshold $\underline{\tau}(c)$, the certifier strictly prefers

to increase the fee, because this increases the demand for disclosure by shifting the threshold further into the lower tail (by Proposition 1). In other words, by increasing the fee, the certifier can sustain increasingly skeptical market beliefs, under which choosing not to disclose indicates highly unfavorable lower-tail outcomes. Intuitively, in this equilibrium, a high fee conveys, by revealed preference, that non-disclosure must be associated with particularly adverse realizations.

Under the upper threshold $\bar{\tau}(c)$, a higher fee conveys, conversely, that only firms with highly favorable information are willing to pay for certification. The higher the fee, the more favorable the disclosed information must be, whereas the information conveyed by non-disclosure remains comparably flat, and hence the lower the probability of disclosure. This creates a trade-off between earning greater revenue per disclosing firm and reducing total demand, given by $1 - \Phi\left(\frac{\bar{\tau}(c)}{\sigma}\right)$. Which side of this trade-off dominates is, in general, ambiguous. When c_0 is small, $\bar{V}(c)$ may initially increase near c_0 . However, for larger c_0 or sufficiently high fees, the certifier's profit must eventually decline with c , implying from continuity the following candidate maximal profit to the certifier.

Lemma 5. *There exists $\bar{V}^{**} = \max_{c \geq c_0} \bar{V}(c)$.*

4.2 Optimal Fee

Expanding on Lemmas 4 and 5, we now examine the solution to the certifier's problem as a function of \bar{c} . To characterize this solution, we consider different values of \bar{c} and later endogenize it through an ex-ante participation decision by firms. This decision can be interpreted as the firm's choice to become publicly traded, to solicit uninformed investors, to establish a reputation that entails public disclosures, or to develop a potentially certifiable information system.

Proposition 2. *If \bar{c} is sufficiently large¹³ (i.e., $\bar{c} \geq \underline{V}^{-1}(c_0)$), the fee c^* and implied disclosure threshold $\tau(c^*)$ are an equilibrium if and only if $\tau(c) = \bar{\tau}(c)$ for any $c > c^*$ and either (i) $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(c^*)$, or (ii) $\tau(c^*) = \bar{\tau}(c^*)$ with $\bar{V}(c^*) \geq c_0$.*

Under the lower threshold $\underline{\tau}(c^*)$ (i), the certifier always prefers to increase the fee as long as the lower threshold is expected. This generates high-profit equilibria with a high frequency of

¹³In the supplementary appendix, we characterize the equilibrium for any \bar{c} .

disclosure, such that further fee increases $c > c^*$ are disciplined with a less favorable equilibrium expectation $\tau(c) = \bar{\tau}(c)$. The equilibrium preferred by the certifier is $c^* = c_0$ with $\tau(c) = \underline{\tau}(c)$, since it jointly exhibits the highest fee and probability of disclosure.

While equilibria (i) always exist, this is not necessarily the case for an equilibrium (ii) with the upper threshold $\bar{\tau}(c^*)$. To see this, consider the case depicted in Figure 6, where $\bar{V}(c)$ is decreasing. Then, $\bar{V}^{**} < c_0$ so that no such fee would be chosen against (near) full-disclosure with $c < c_0$. This in turn rules out the possibility of *any* threshold $\bar{\tau}(c)$. Indeed, Lemma 4 shows that a sufficient condition for the profit of the certifier to be decreasing given $\bar{\tau}(c)$, and thus lower than $\bar{V}(c_0) < c_0$, is that

$$\frac{c_0}{\sigma} \lambda\left(\frac{\tau(c_0)}{\sigma}\right) > 1. \quad (11)$$

Corollary 3. *Suppose that \bar{c} is sufficiently large. If (11) holds, which occurs if s is sufficiently large, any equilibrium must be of the form (iii.a), i.e., $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(c^*)$ (lower threshold). Otherwise (iii.b) is an equilibrium if and only if $\bar{V}(c^*) = \bar{V}^{**} \geq c_0$.*

In summary, we show in Corollary 3 that, given sufficient noise and an endogenous choice of fee, the *lower* threshold is the only outcome consistent with equilibrium. This result is obtained from the certifier's optimal choice of fee consistent with equilibrium, not from imposing a refinement. Intuitively, with enough noise, the certifier holds a valuable option to implement full disclosure, which dominates any fee with the upper threshold. Yet, because full disclosure is itself incompatible with equilibrium, equilibrium expectations must settle on the low-threshold equilibrium with, possibly, even higher profits for the certifier.

4.3 Equilibrium Selection

Until this point, we characterized the equilibria of the game without invoking any refinements. We consider next whether intuitive refinements may help reduce the set of equilibria.

A feature of certain equilibria in (iii.a) is that any $c < \bar{c}$ must be disciplined by a discontinuity between the equilibrium path $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(c^*)$ and other $c > c^*$ which must satisfy $\tau(c) = \bar{\tau}(c)$; otherwise the certifier would continue to increase c to induce further disclosure. This discontinuity

is counterintuitive, because for $c > c^*$, the equilibrium $\underline{\tau}(c)$ continues to exist, and one might have reasonably expected market beliefs to adjust smoothly, whenever feasible, rather than coordinate on an otherwise arbitrary threshold c^* beyond which the equilibrium expectation abruptly shifts.

Assumption (C). Let C (given by (c_0, ∞)) denote the set of costs such that the subgame equilibrium is not unique. Then, $\tau(c)$ is continuous for any c in the interior of C .

Condition (C) rules out discontinuities in the equilibrium threshold as costs vary when multiple subgame equilibria coexist. In particular, it excludes abrupt discontinuities arising from arbitrary switches between the two threshold equilibria when there is no discontinuity in the primitives, except in cases where the equilibrium is unique (e.g., unravelling) and there is no scope for belief selection. Accordingly, we focus on equilibria that do not rely on ad hoc, cost-triggered belief discontinuities in otherwise smooth environments without any exogenous public coordination device or institutionally driven regime shifts.¹⁴ Proposition 14 in the supplementary appendix provides a robustness foundation for Assumption (C) by considering a perturbation that smooths investors' informational environment. The basic idea is simple: if investors observe fees with an arbitrarily small amount of payoff-irrelevant noise, and if their continuation beliefs do not exhibit discontinuous jumps across nearby observed fee realizations, then the selected equilibrium threshold must change continuously with the fee. Combining with cases in which (iii.b) does not arise, the equilibrium fee is always maximal and is set at $c^* = \bar{c}$, with the lower threshold prevailing.

Proposition 3. *Suppose \bar{c} is sufficiently large and (C) is imposed on off-equilibrium beliefs. Then, if (11) holds, the equilibrium is unique with $c^* = \bar{c}$ and $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(\bar{c})$.*

The intuition for this result is that the payoff attainable arbitrarily close to c_0 serves as a commitment to seek a profit strictly greater than c_0 . No such solution exists for fees below c_0 , and if no equilibrium exists under $\bar{\tau}(c)$ either, the market must expect the lower threshold. Then,

¹⁴Assumption (C) is a refinement suited to smooth environments without such external regime changes, as studied here. In a large decentralized capital market, coordination on arbitrary equilibrium changes is not straightforward absent some special device. In contrast, when there is an explicit public coordination device, a discrete institutional threshold, or a regulatory regime shift, discontinuities in the equilibrium threshold may be economically meaningful rather than arbitrary. In such cases, switches between equilibria are driven by an additional public state variable.

by continuity, the certifier can progressively increase the fee, which unambiguously increases its profit. The resulting outcome is a fee that attains its upper bound \bar{c} .

The argument used in proposition 3 may not be sufficient if the probability of disclosure is very high under c_0 , in which case (11) no longer holds and there is an interior choice of fee achieving \bar{V}^{**} . While the certifier now achieves a greater profit under $\bar{\tau}(c)$, this serves to break the necessity of $\underline{\tau}(c)$ and therefore can hurt the certifier.¹⁵ To address this case, we consider an alternative approach by appealing to a refinement that rationalizes the certifier's behavior. Specifically, we apply the forward induction refinement of Govindan and Wilson (2009) and Man (2012) to our setting. These are special cases of a broader class of forward induction criteria, under which beliefs at later stages must assume rationality in earlier actions, even when those actions occur off the equilibrium path. For expositional clarity, we focus below on the intuition and defer the formalism to the Appendix.

The forward induction logic operates as follows. Upon observing any fee c , investors should, whenever possible, interpret this choice as rational, meaning that the certifier expected $\tau(c)$ to yield a higher profit than any guaranteed payoff from alternative strategies. We show that the equilibrium with $\tau(c^*) = \bar{\tau}(c^*)$ does not survive this refinement. The intuition is as follows. By playing c^* , the certifier secures a profit of $c^*(1 - \Phi(\frac{\bar{\tau}(c^*)}{\sigma}))$. Now suppose investors observe a fee $c > c^*$. If they were to anticipate $\bar{\tau}(c)$, this move would be irrational, since raising c would give them lower profit than what they could have obtained by playing c^* . To rationalize the certifier's move, it must be that the certifier anticipated the lower-threshold equilibrium $\underline{\tau}(c)$. Given this off-equilibrium belief, the certifier is indeed better-off, because $\underline{\tau}(c) < \bar{\tau}(c)$ implies a higher profit than at c^* . Thus, the equilibrium with $\bar{\tau}(c^*)$ fails the forward induction test.

Proposition 4. *If off-equilibrium beliefs must satisfy the requirement in Govindan and Wilson (2009) and Man (2012), the forward induction equilibrium is unique with $c^* = \bar{c}$.*

The forward induction argument implies that, when investors observe a fee too high to be consistent with profit maximization under $\bar{\tau}(c)$, they should infer that the certifier expected the

¹⁵It can be shown, albeit numerically, that cases in which \bar{V}^{**} is the global maximum of $V(c)$ require the noise to be small; in particular, if $s > 0.4\sigma$, the profit function $\bar{V}(c)$ decreases for all $c \geq c_0$ and, therefore, $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(\bar{c})$ cannot be an equilibrium.

more profitable $\underline{\tau}(c)$ equilibrium to prevail. As a result, the high fee serves as a coordination device and the certifier, knowing of the forward induction reasoning, successfully achieves their preferred threshold $\underline{\tau}(\bar{c})$.¹⁶

5 Discussion and Extensions

5.1 Bounded Support and General Distributions

Until now, we specialized the analysis to normal distributions for tractability, which allows us to use projection theorems and obtain closed-form expressions for posterior beliefs. Conceptually, however, neither normality nor unbounded support are essential. In particular, the key arguments from Section 3 rely only on the fact that disclosure generates a noisy but informative signal that is more likely under higher firm values, and on the way in which truncation of the prior modifies investors' beliefs after disclosure or non-disclosure.¹⁷

In this subsection we allow for a general (not necessarily normal) prior and only impose mild regularity conditions that guarantee the shape properties used in Section 3. Throughout, \tilde{v} denotes the firm's private information, $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ the independent certification noise, and $\tilde{x} = \tilde{v} + \tilde{\varepsilon}$ the publicly observed signal upon disclosure. Given a conjectured threshold strategy $d(v) = \mathbf{1}\{v \geq \tau\}$, prices continue to be determined by Bayes' rule as in (3): $P(x) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} \geq \tau, x)$, and $P(\emptyset) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} < \tau)$, and a finite threshold τ is a (candidate) equilibrium cutoff if and only if the marginal firm is indifferent, $\mathbb{E}P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) - c = P(\emptyset)$, where, as before, we suppress the dependence of $P(\cdot)$ on the conjectured threshold whenever this does not create confusion.

¹⁶We do not claim that all forward induction criteria necessarily eliminate the equilibrium with $\bar{\tau}(c^*)$. Several forward induction refinements, such as those based solely on iterative admissibility (Pearce, 1984; Battigalli and Siniscalchi, 2002) or on elimination of dominated strategies (Ben-Porath and Dekel, 1992; Shimoji and Watson, 1998), may have limited effect in our context, since the certifier could always hold optimistic beliefs that all firms will certify. Our refinement follows Man (2012) in requiring that investors interpret off-equilibrium moves through a rational lens, i.e., by attributing a plausible profit motive to the certifier.

¹⁷A potential concern with the normal benchmark is that unbounded support can generate counterintuitive implications such as unbounded certification fees in the absence of an exogenous upper bound \bar{c} . These should be interpreted as "very large" fees in a stylized model rather than literally infinite fees. Still, it is useful to show that our equilibrium characterization does not rely on unbounded support. In particular, if the fundamentals are bounded, the value of separating from the worst type is itself bounded, so that beyond some fee level no firm is willing to purchase certification and the unique equilibrium is no-disclosure.

We now state primitive assumptions under which the expected payoff of the marginal discloser is increasing in the threshold. First, \tilde{v} is absolutely integrable with a continuous strictly positive density $f_v(\cdot)$ and support in $[\underline{v}, \bar{v}]$, such that \underline{v} and \bar{v} are finite. Second, the noise $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ is independent of \tilde{v} , has a strictly positive, continuous, log-concave density f_ε on \mathbb{R} , and mean zero; therefore, the signal structure $x = \tilde{v} + \tilde{\varepsilon}$ satisfies the monotone likelihood ratio property (MLRP). It follows that the equilibria still feature a threshold disclosure strategy.¹⁸ Let the marginal discloser's benefit from disclosure be $\psi(\tau) \equiv \mathbb{E}P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) - P(\emptyset)$, which is strictly positive for every interior τ . A subgame equilibrium threshold τ is then characterized by $\psi(\tau) = c$. Further, $\psi(\tau)$ is continuous in τ on the compact interval $[\underline{v}, \bar{v}]$ and hence attains a finite minimum and maximum, with

$$0 < c_0 \equiv \min_{\tau \in [\underline{v}, \bar{v}]} \psi(\tau) \leq \max_{\tau \in [\underline{v}, \bar{v}]} \psi(\tau) \equiv c_1 < \infty.$$

Under bounded support, ψ is bounded above. Thus, there exists a finite maximal cost c_1 below which disclosure can arise in equilibrium. By contrast, no such finite upper bound exists in the unbounded baseline model, as implied by Proposition 1.

Proposition 5. *The disclosure subgame for a given fee c has the following properties:*

- (i) *if $c < c_0$, the unique subgame equilibrium is full disclosure, i.e., $\tau(c) = \underline{v}$;*
- (ii) *if $c \in [c_0, c_1]$, there exists at least one subgame equilibrium threshold τ^* solving $\psi(\tau^*) = c$;*
- (iii) *if $c > c_1$, the unique subgame equilibrium is no disclosure, i.e., $\tau(c) = \bar{v}$;*
- (iv) *if, in addition, $\tau_0 \in (\underline{v}, \bar{v})$ is a local minimizer of ψ and $c \in (\psi(\tau_0), \min\{\psi(\bar{v}), \psi(\underline{v})\})$, then there exist at least two distinct equilibrium thresholds $\underline{\tau}(c) < \tau_0 < \bar{\tau}(c)$ satisfying $\psi(\bar{\tau}(c)) = \psi(\underline{\tau}(c)) = c$.*¹⁹

Proposition 5 shows that the qualitative structure of equilibria in the disclosure subgame is robust to relaxing normality. The only property of the primitives that matters is the range of the

¹⁸This result, under bounded support and a general distribution, is formally established in Lemma 10 of the supplementary appendix.

¹⁹What the proposition, as stated, does *not* say is whether the region with multiple equilibria is non-empty; for example, if $\psi(\tau)$ is minimized in the boundaries, the equilibrium is always unique. However, we show in a supplementary appendix that under reasonable conditions, namely that distributions are logconcave, noise is symmetric, and the mass in the upper bound is zero (which will hold letting $\bar{v} \rightarrow \infty$), $c_0 < \min\{\psi(\bar{v}), \psi(\underline{v})\}$, which demonstrates that τ_0 is interior and there is always a range of costs with two equilibria as $c \downarrow \psi(\tau_0)$.

disclosure benefit $\psi(\tau)$ to the marginal discloser, which is determined by the distribution of \tilde{v} and the informativeness of the noisy signal $\tilde{x} = \tilde{v} + \tilde{\varepsilon}$. For low fees $c < c_0$, the payoff to disclosing is always strictly greater than non-disclosure, so that the unique equilibrium unravels to full disclosure ($\tau(c) = \underline{v}$). At the other extreme, for potentially high fees $c > c_1$, under bounded support, the cost of disclosure may be higher than any benefit and a non-disclosure equilibrium ensues ($\tau(c) = \bar{v}$). In-between these values, multiple partial-disclosure equilibria may occur. Indeed, as long as the net benefit ψ is minimized for a threshold τ_0 interior to $[\underline{v}, \bar{v}]$, there will be a non-empty region of values with at least two equilibria with properties similar to the benchmark model.

We illustrate this proposition by assuming that \tilde{v} is truncated normal with a lower truncation at η ; given that the mean of \tilde{v} remains normalized to zero, one can interpret η as the net difference between the actual expected value and a point involving limited liability (any residual claim that shareholders may be able to extract over other claimants if the firm goes bankrupt). For our purpose, η could be positive or negative. It is clear that the price in equation (2) remains unchanged because the lower truncation does not affect the conditional distribution with $v \geq \tau$. What does change is the fact that $\tau \geq \eta$ and the non-disclosure price must now be stated in terms of the truncated distribution:

$$P(\emptyset) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} \in [\eta, \tau]) = \sigma \frac{\phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma}) - \phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})}{\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})}. \quad (12)$$

In Figure 7 (left), this yields similar intuitions except that the non-disclosure price is now flatter and, if η is large enough, there can only be a unique equilibrium.

Truncated normal model ($\eta = -2, \sigma = 1, s = 2$)

Dye model ($s = -2, \sigma = 1, q = 0.2$)

Figure 7: Disclosure thresholds for other models for $P(\emptyset)$.

An immediate corollary is that, relative to the classical noiseless benchmark, noisy information processing strictly enlarges the set of disclosure costs for which the game unravels to full disclosure. Under perfect disclosure, the marginal discloser receives exactly τ . As the threshold approaches full disclosure, the net benefit from disclosure goes to zero. Then no positive cost can sustain full disclosure. With noisy processing, by contrast, the marginal discloser is pooled with higher types, raising the expected disclosure payoff above the realized type and creating a region of positive costs under which full disclosure arises.

Corollary 4. *Let $c_0^s \equiv \sup\{c \geq 0 : \text{there exists an equilibrium in which } \tau(c) = \underline{v}\}$ be the maximal cost at which full disclosure is sustained under noise $\tilde{\varepsilon} \sim N(0, s^2)$. Then $c_0^0 = 0 < c_0^s$ for all $s > 0$.*

Note that, under bounded support, $c_1 < \infty$ and disclosure eventually shuts down once $c > c_1$ by Proposition 5. By contrast, in the unbounded normal baseline, Proposition 1 implies that the lower-threshold equilibrium exists for arbitrarily large fees and satisfies $\underline{\tau}(c) \rightarrow -\infty$ as $c \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, bounded support affects equilibrium outcomes in the tail at large fees. However, it leaves unchanged the local forces that generate multiplicity of equilibria and the comparative statics of the thresholds. In other words, boundedness only limits how far the mechanism can operate by imposing a finite cap c_1 on the maximum disclosure benefit.

Proposition 6. *Suppose that $\tau_0 \in (\underline{v}, \bar{v})$ is a local minimizer of ψ . For $c \in (\psi(\tau_0), \min\{\psi(\bar{v}), \psi(\underline{v})\})$, the equation $\psi(\tau) = c$ admits two distinct solutions $\underline{\tau}(c) < \tau_0 < \bar{\tau}(c)$, where $\psi(\underline{\tau}(c)) = \psi(\bar{\tau}(c)) = c$ and there is no other solution to $\psi(\tau) = c$ in $(\underline{\tau}(c), \bar{\tau}(c))$. Then $\underline{\tau}(c)$ decreases with c and $\bar{\tau}(c)$ increases with c for $c \in (\psi(\tau_0), \min\{\psi(\bar{v}), \psi(\underline{v})\})$.*

As shown in Proposition 5, there are two equilibria near the interior minimizer τ_0 when the condition in part (iv) holds: $\underline{\tau}(c)$ is the solution to $\psi(\tau) = c$ immediately to the left of τ_0 , while $\bar{\tau}(c)$ is the solution immediately to the right. Similar to the baseline, as c increases above $\psi(\tau_0)$, the interval $\{\tau : \psi(\tau) < c\}$ around τ_0 expands, and its left endpoint moves left and its right endpoint moves right. Thus, whenever ψ has an interior minimum, the lower-threshold equilibrium exhibits more disclosure as fees increase over the relevant range,²⁰ while the upper-threshold equilibrium

²⁰We show in the supplementary appendix that such a region of fees must exist when ψ has an interior minimum.

exhibits less.²¹

5.2 Uncertain Information Endowment

We now examine the effect of investor uncertainty in an alternative environment where certification is costless, but firms face uncertainty regarding their information endowment (Dye, 1985). The assumptions of the baseline model remain unchanged, except that (i) the cost is set to $c = 0$, and (ii) the firm may be uninformed or unable to disclose with probability $q \in (0, 1)$. In that case, we exogenously impose $d(v) = \emptyset$; with complementary probability $1 - q$, the firm can choose its disclosure policy optimally, $d(v) \in \{v, \emptyset\}$.²²

Since disclosure is costless, the indifference condition becomes $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})] = P(\emptyset)$. The expected price conditional on disclosure, $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})]$, is identical to expression (8). Holding fixed the conjectured threshold, an observed disclosure indicates that the firm is able to disclose, and thus the Bayesian updating is the same as in the baseline model. This function increases monotonically in τ from $-\infty$ to ∞ .²³

The non-disclosure price $P(\emptyset)$ must incorporate the probability that the firm is unable to disclose. As shown in Jung and Kwon (1988), this expectation is

$$P(\emptyset) = \frac{q\mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}) + (1 - q)F(\tau)\mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} \leq \tau)}{q + (1 - q)F(\tau)}. \quad (13)$$

Importantly, Acharya et al. (2011) show that this non-disclosure price is U-shaped, attaining its minimum at $\tau(0)$, defined as the equilibrium in Jung and Kwon (1988) when there is no noise ($s = 0$). The next proposition characterizes the resulting equilibrium.

²¹See Proposition 18 in the supplementary appendix for an illustration. For a truncated normal with lower truncation at η , lowering η sufficiently allows the bounded model to approximate the unbounded baseline over any fixed range of fees. That is, as η decreases, the truncated model converges to the unbounded model. As η increases, however, the non-disclosure price flattens and multiplicity may disappear. Once the threshold approaches the lower bound, the market can no longer make non-disclosure arbitrarily punitive. As a result, the lower threshold cannot fall indefinitely, and there exists a finite fee above which the unique equilibrium is no disclosure.

²²For expositional simplicity, we maintain the assumption of normally distributed noise to remain consistent with the baseline model. The formal argument, however, holds generally as long as the signal structure satisfies the monotone likelihood ratio property.

²³The uniqueness of the equilibrium requires only that $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})]$ be monotonic, which holds under any signal structure satisfying the monotone likelihood ratio property.

Proposition 7. *There is a unique equilibrium given by a threshold $\tau(s) \leq \tau(0)$. The probability of disclosure is increasing in s and decreasing in σ .*

As shown in Figure 7 (right), the model now features a unique equilibrium with partial disclosure, and the probability of disclosure is monotonically increasing in the level of noise. A new result in this class of models is that, unlike in Jung and Kwon (1988), the probability of disclosure depends on fundamental uncertainty σ *when noise is present*. That is, in the benchmark model without noise, and under the assumption of a constant q , the disclosure probability would not vary with σ (Peris, 2025). With noisy processing, however, this irrelevance breaks down: the probability of disclosure decreases in environments with greater fundamental uncertainty. That is, the uncertainty mutes the effect of noise, making it relatively easier to separate out the marginal discloser, thereby weakening incentives to disclose. This comparative static is opposite to that in Verrecchia (1990), where higher uncertainty leads to more disclosure in the absence of noise and may help distinguish between types of frictions. Banerjee et al. (2024) similarly emphasize that the friction driving non-disclosure matters for the comparative statics of disclosure probability, albeit through a different channel.²⁴

5.3 Endogenous Noise

So far, we have treated the processing noise s as an inherent friction tied to the nature of information communicated by the firm, e.g., complexity, credibility, or processing uncertainty. We now consider a variation in which the firm endogenously controls the level of noise. This is, admittedly, an extreme assumption but serves to illustrate, in the most direct manner possible, the firm's incentives to strategically influence how effectively information is processed. There are many possible choices over timing and observability so, to make a baseline choice, we assume that s is privately known and chosen by the firm at the start of the game before it observes its fundamental value v . Although we later discuss other choices over timing and observability, we explain this choice as our starting point below, starting with alternative information structures.

²⁴The key distinction in Banerjee et al. (2024) lies in the shape of beliefs under non-disclosure, whereas our mechanism centers on the interaction between fundamental uncertainty and noise that affects the pooling benefit of disclosure.

A different timing would be to choose the noise after fundamentals v are observed. We do not formally solve for this ex-post environment, because it is already discussed in prior literature (Aghamolla and Smith 2023) and in our setting, would not yield additional new implications beyond incentives for firms with bad news to strategically obfuscate.²⁵

Another (reasonable) alternative assumption is whether s is observable, which may be plausible in certain settings but implicitly involves an additional source of information. Because there is no practical disclosure of s in the real world, it is an empirical question as to whether investors are fully aware of this uncertainty, or completely unaware, with the reality likely somewhere in-between. For presentation purposes, however, observability of s requires yet another secondary modelling choice as to whether s is observed before or after c is observed. So, for expositional purposes, we defer a complete discussion until the intuitions without observability are fully expressed.

In what follows, we thus assume as baseline that s is chosen ex-ante by the firm and unobserved. We need only adjust the prices $P(x)$ in (5) to be a function of a market belief \hat{s} about noise, hereafter, denoted $\hat{P}(x)$. Then, the firm's optimal choice of noise is to maximize

$$s^* \in \max_s V(s) \equiv \mathbb{E}(\max(P(\emptyset), \mathbb{E}_\varepsilon \hat{P}(v + \varepsilon))), \quad (14)$$

where, in the above expression, only ε depends on the actual s while beliefs depend on the conjectured noise \hat{s} . Then, a policy that maximizes $\mathbb{E}_\varepsilon P(v + \varepsilon|\hat{s})$ for any v must necessarily maximize the firm's expected payoff. The next lemma characterizes this solution.

Lemma 6. $\mathbb{E}_\varepsilon P(v + \varepsilon|\hat{s})$ is increasing in s , i.e., $V(s)$ is increasing in s .

Since Lemma 6 suggests that the firm would always prefer more noise, it is interesting to look at the limiting case with $s = \hat{s} \rightarrow \infty$, in which case the certified message no longer contains useful information beyond the fact that $v \geq \tau$, so that the indifference condition reduces to $P(\emptyset) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} < \tau) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} \geq \tau) - c$, which can be rewritten as

²⁵In practice, it is of an empirical question which timing is most descriptive, and the answer to this question may depend on types of obfuscation. On the one hand, the firm may omit strategically important details or bury them in footnotes, making processing more complicated. Alternatively, the firm may spend more time collecting and organizing its information to make it more readable, which would occur early in its reporting period before all uncertainty is resolved.

$$c = \mathbb{E}[v|v \geq \tau] - \mathbb{E}[v|v < \tau] = \frac{\sigma \phi\left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right)}{\Phi\left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) (1 - \Phi\left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right))}. \quad (15)$$

Lemma 7. *The function $\mathbb{E}[v|v \geq \tau] - \mathbb{E}[v|v < \tau]$ is U-shaped in τ with a minimum at $\tau = 0$ and unbounded range $[4\sigma/\sqrt{2\pi}, \infty)$ and its minimum at $\tau = 0$.*

It follows readily from Lemma 7 that the main characteristics are preserved even if noise is arbitrarily large, as we characterize below.²⁶

Proposition 8. *Let $c_0 = 4\sigma/\sqrt{2\pi}$, then $s = \infty$ and*

- (i) *if $c < c_0$, the equilibrium unravels to full-disclosure;*
- (ii) *if $c = c_0$, there is a unique equilibrium with $\tau = \mathbb{E}(v)$ such that half of the firms disclose;*
- (iii) *if $c > c_0$, there are two distinct equilibria $\underline{\tau}(c) < 0 < \bar{\tau}(c)$, with $|\underline{\tau}(c)|, \bar{\tau}(c) \rightarrow \infty$.*

It may seem surprising that the firm pays a cost for an uninformative signal but the intuition is similar to Lizzeri (1999); namely, the firm that does not make the disclosure must be perceived as a low type, which in turn penalizes it and provides incentives to buy the certification. Indeed, the unravelling equilibrium is unique for a finite non-zero cost even if the signal is uninformative. Unlike this earlier study, however, the model does not necessarily imply full surplus extraction. Further, unlike this earlier study, we show that purchasing an uninformative signal is informative. Finally, as in the baseline, there are two equilibria, with $\underline{\tau}(c)$ featuring more disclosure.

As in the baseline model, the certifier always prefers the equilibrium with more disclosure $\underline{\tau}(c)$ and, in this equilibrium, would choose the highest possible fee, given that it further increases the probability of certification. Unlike in the baseline however, we can now explicitly characterize the optimal fee under $\bar{\tau}(c)$: using the value of c from (15), the profit to the certifier is

$$\bar{\Pi}(c) = c(1 - \Phi\left(\frac{\bar{\tau}(c)}{\sigma}\right)) = \frac{\sigma \phi\left(\frac{\bar{\tau}(c)}{\sigma}\right)}{\Phi\left(\frac{\bar{\tau}(c)}{\sigma}\right)}.$$

²⁶Note that this limit, or the implied equilibrium results, does not reconcile with the results in Marinovic and Sridhar (2015) under their pointwise linear approximation of the expectation, further demonstrating that this approximation is improper even if the noise is large. By contrast, we take here the (correct) limit of the equilibrium indifference condition as $s \rightarrow \infty$.

The term on the right-hand side is decreasing in $\bar{\tau}(c)$, which demonstrates that the certifier would never choose to increase c above c_0 under $\bar{\tau}(c)$. Of course, $c = c_0$ cannot be an equilibrium since the certifier would be better-off slightly decreasing c to generate unravelling, nor any $c < c_0$ from the symmetric reasoning that the certifier could (slightly) increase c toward c_0 . We are thus left with the following implication.

Proposition 9. *In all equilibria of the certification game with endogenous choice of s (and finite fee c^*), it must hold that: (i) $s^* = \infty$, (ii) $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(c^*)$ and $\tau(c) = \bar{\tau}(c)$ for $c > c^*$. Further, a sufficient condition for c^* to be an equilibrium is that c^* be sufficiently large so that (given that $\underline{\tau}(c)$ is diverging toward $-\infty$ as c increases), $\phi\left(\frac{\tau(c^*)}{\sigma}\right) / \Phi\left(\frac{\tau(c^*)}{\sigma}\right) \geq 4/(\sqrt{2\pi})$.*

In summary, there is a continuum of equilibria of the game with endogenous certification fee, and they always feature partial disclosure with a finite fee and a completely uninformative message. We also show that, without appealing to a refinement, these equilibria must feature the threshold $\bar{\tau}(c^*)$. Finally, this equilibrium must feature more profit for the certifier than the (feasible) choice to achieve unravelling.²⁷

²⁷The assumption that s is unobserved is critical for these insights, because it allows the firm to increase its noise to fool market expectations. In equilibrium, the market must expect that the message would be (in the limit) uninformative. This is of course a stylized, rather than descriptive, intuition serving to show what the firm's incentives are. For completeness, we briefly discuss the case of s being observable.

To begin with, suppose that s is chosen after c is known (or for an exogenous c). In this case, for any given c , the expected market price must be equal to the expectation $\mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}) = 0$, so that the firm no longer receives any benefit from manipulating market expectations. The firm still bears a potential cost of certification so its choice of s can be summarized to minimizing the probability of incurring the cost $(1 - \Phi(\tau(c, s)/s))$, where the threshold is now a function of both c and s . As shown earlier, this implies that, if $\bar{\tau}(c, s)$ is expected, the probability of disclosure is increasing in the noise and the firm would optimally choose s as small as possible, while the opposite holds if $\underline{\tau}(c, s)$ is expected. We conclude that the preferences of the firm in the observable noise model are ambiguous. Of course, the multiplicity is greatly increased because which of the two thresholds is played could also be a function of the publicly observed s .

A variation on this setting may involve choosing s before c is chosen, i.e., the firm chooses a policy on a pure ex-ante basis in a manner that is likely less flexible than a certifier's pricing decision. If this is possible, the firm can protect itself against the threshold $\underline{\tau}(c, s)$ by choosing zero noise since, in this case, the multiplicity does not occur. Therefore, the timing in this case gives the ability to the firm to entirely rule out the most informative equilibrium. Of course, this insight depends on the (possibly strong) assumption that exactly zero noise is attainable. If noise has a lower bound, then the same forces as in the case of choosing noise post c will apply.

5.4 Competition via other information sources

We illustrate below that competition between certifiers does not change the main mechanisms of the model, as long as, obviously, we are not placed in a situation where certifiers compete on prices with *exactly* the same signal, that is, perfectly correlated errors.

To set intuition, consider the strongest form of competition where, in addition to the certifier modelled in the baseline, there is a competitive set of other information intermediaries who sell a signal $x_2 = v + \varepsilon_2$, where $Var(\varepsilon_2) = s_2$, at a cost that, to make the competition as severe as possibly imaginable, we set equal to zero and assume it can be acquired and disclosed prior to the start of the game to best neutralize the function of the certifier. This implies the following extended multivariate form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} v \\ x \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} \sim N \left(\mathbf{0}, \begin{pmatrix} \sigma^2 & \sigma^2 & \sigma^2 \\ \sigma^2 & \sigma^2 + s^2 & \sigma^2 + \rho_{\varepsilon\varepsilon_2} s s_2 \\ \sigma^2 & \sigma^2 + \rho_{\varepsilon\varepsilon_2} s s' & \sigma^2 + s_2^2 \end{pmatrix} \right), \quad (16)$$

where we allow for this additional information to be correlated with both v and ε , as long as this correlation is not perfect, i.e., this covariance matrix has full rank. It is then readily verified that this model maps back to our baseline after readjusting posteriors conditional on the signal x' being acquired, that is, relabelling $\sigma' \equiv Var(v|x_2) = \sigma^2(1 - \rho_{vx_2}^2)$ and $s' \equiv Var(\varepsilon|x_2) = s^2(1 - \rho_{\varepsilon x_2}^2)$.

As a result, the effect of competition, to the extent that it provides additional information, is not to change the qualitative implication of the model (which hold for any σ and s). Competition via signals that are informative about v will be equivalent to a reduction in σ while signals informative about processing errors will, as is intuitive, reduce s .²⁸

An important caveat is that our intent in this section is solely to show the robustness of the argument to potential competition, so that it is made clear that our restriction to a single intermediary is only used to keep the model as minimal as possible. However, we do not evaluate the effect of

²⁸Perhaps a more interesting question is to solve for a competitive model with two otherwise ex-ante similar certifiers with correlated signals choosing their fees simultaneously. However, while the joint signal would affect residual uncertainty, it is not clear what additional questions would be asked in this setting beyond explicitly solving the model. As we have shown, the addition of competition need not remove the main forces and may increase or decrease disclosure depending on which equilibrium is played.

competition of market outcomes, which would likely require its own model. For completeness, we briefly provide below preliminary conjectures, educated by our previous analysis, for such a model.

While the timing is unchanged, suppose that there are n certifiers, whose fees c_i are indexed by i and issuing a (for simplicity) symmetric noisy signal $x_i = v + \varepsilon_i$, where ε_i are uncorrelated white noise with variance s .²⁹ We consider first the certifier's choice and conjecture an equilibrium in which the (symmetric) strategy is to buy all signals when $v \geq \tau(\sum c_i)$ and buy no signal otherwise. These equilibria can always be sustained as long as selectively buying signals would involve unfavorable expectations; more generally, selective buying equilibria are more difficult to sustain because the firm reveals that it does not have good fundamentals by buying fewer signals, offsetting the potential effect of signal noise. Also, on a symmetric equilibrium path, certifiers will choose the same fee. It is readily seen that, under this conjecture, the firm's problem is identical to the baseline, with two adjustments: (i) $s' = s/n$ as the residual noise is reduced, and (ii) the relevant cost is $C = \sum c_i$. The main insights from the baseline are unchanged, and can then be obtained from the comparative statics on s' and C . In particular, holding the total fee fixed, more competition will tend to increase disclosure under $\bar{\tau}$ but decrease it under $\underline{\tau}$ via its effect on s' .

Moving to the certifiers' problem, under $\underline{\tau}$, any increase in the fee will continue to increase the probability of disclosure, so incentives to increase the fee are unchanged in this equilibrium. Under $\bar{\tau}$, the objective function is slightly changed, because a competitor receives $c_i(1 - \Phi(\bar{\tau}(c_i + \sum_{j \neq i} c_j)/\sigma))$, whose derivative in c_i is *higher* than in the baseline objective $C(1 - \Phi(\bar{\tau}(C)/\sigma))$, i.e, the competitive firm earns a lower profit per disclosure. This counter-intuitive aspect suggests that competition may not necessarily reduce fees.

²⁹It can be verified that this is purely for expositional purposes, but the argument would hold if the signals were (imperfectly) correlated or with different precisions. One conceptual advantage of the symmetric certifiers is that it makes more intuitive sense to focus on symmetric equilibria (even though symmetric equilibria would exist even if the signals were not similar).

6 Conclusion

This paper examines how noisy information processing interacts with disclosure frictions. A firm privately observes its fundamental information and chooses whether to disclose for a cost to produce a verifiable, but noisily processed, report. Investors price the firm based on their processed report combined with conjectures about the firm's disclosure strategy. Even in this simple environment, adding realistic noise to the report has sharp implications for the existence, structure, and comparative statics of voluntary disclosure equilibria.

Our first main insight is that any amount of processing noise generically overturns the classical result of a unique partial-disclosure equilibrium. When the certifier's fee is low, the unique equilibrium exhibits full disclosure, so even modest noise does not prevent unraveling. As the fee increases beyond a critical cost c_0 , the model typically admits two distinct threshold equilibria: one with relatively high disclosure and one with relatively low disclosure. This multiplicity arises because noise alters not only how investors interpret disclosures, but also the inference when remaining silent relative to those reports.

Second, the model delivers comparative statics that differ from the benchmark with perfectly precise disclosure. In the low-disclosure equilibrium, comparative statics seem familiar: disclosure tends to decrease as disclosure becomes more costly or more precise, and increase with the variance of fundamentals. In the high-disclosure equilibrium, however, the relationship between disclosure and frictions can be reversed or non-monotonic: lower noise or higher costs is associated with more disclosure, and changes in uncertainty can push the equilibrium toward full disclosure. These results highlight that empirical patterns linking disclosure to frictions may depend critically on which equilibrium the capital market will coordinate on.

Third, by endogenizing the cost as a fee charged by a third party, we link equilibrium selection to the economics of certification. A profit-maximizing certifier chooses fees knowing that the disclosure subgame may admit multiple equilibria. As a result, some parameter configurations lead to high-fee/high-disclosure regimes, whereas others favor low-fee/low-disclosure regimes. This perspective suggests that observed variation in audit or rating fees and in verification intensity

across settings need not simply reflect cost heterogeneity; it may also reflect different equilibrium regimes induced by noisy processing.

The analysis also yields testable implications for empirical work in accounting and finance. The model predicts that disclosure behavior can switch regimes as costs, uncertainty, or processing noise change, and provides guidance on how to use the overall level of disclosure to infer which comparative statics should be expected in a given environment. For example, in markets or periods with very low disclosure intensity, one should expect conventional comparative statics (disclosure decreasing in costs and increasing in noise and the variance of fundamentals), whereas in high-disclosure environments, the opposite patterns would be expected. We also argue that, across equilibria, joint comparative statics can be tested, with the prediction that noise and the variance of fundamentals affect disclosure in the same direction, and opposite direction to the cost.

The model is deliberately stylized and suggests several avenues for future research. Extending the analysis to dynamic settings, richer heterogeneity in investors' information processing, competition among multiple certifiers, or explicit enforcement and litigation frictions can bring the framework closer to specific institutional questions. Our results indicate that incorporating realistic processing frictions into disclosure models can generate qualitatively new predictions and help reconcile seemingly conflicting empirical findings on the relation between disclosure, verification, and information frictions. We view this as a useful step toward a more complete theory of disclosure in noisy environments.

Appendix

In this appendix, we use $\lambda(z) \equiv \phi(z)/(1 - \Phi(z))$ as the inverse Mill's ratio, with $\phi(z)$ (resp., $\Phi(z)$) indicating the pdf (resp., cdf) of the standard normal distribution. In parts of the proof, we also simplify notations using $\rho \equiv \frac{s}{\sqrt{\sigma^2+s^2}} \in (0, 1)$, $\theta_s(y) \equiv \frac{\tau s/\sigma - \sigma y}{\sqrt{\sigma^2+s^2}} = \frac{\tau\rho}{\sigma} - y\sqrt{1-\rho^2}$, and $\theta \equiv \theta_s(\tilde{Y})$, with \tilde{Y} defined as a standard normal random variable.

Proof of Lemma 1. Let $\Delta(\tau; c) = \mathbb{E}[P(x; c) | v = \tau] - c - P(\emptyset; c)$. Since $P(x; c) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v}|x, \tilde{v} \geq \tau) \geq \tau$ for any x , as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, $P(\tau; c) \rightarrow \infty$, where $P(\emptyset; c) \rightarrow 0$, implying that $\Delta(\tau; c) \rightarrow \infty$. As

$\tau \rightarrow -\infty$, $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{v} \mid x, \tilde{v} > \tau] \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tilde{v} \mid x] = \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2}x$. Hence, $\mathbb{E}[P(x; c) \mid v = \tau] \sim \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2}\tau$, whereas

$$P(\emptyset; c) = -\sigma \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) \sim -\tau. \quad (17)$$

Therefore $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow -\infty} \Delta(\tau; c) = \infty$. Either (a) there exists a finite τ^* with $\Delta(\tau^*; c) = 0$, which yields an interior threshold equilibrium; or (b) $\Delta(\tau; c) > 0$ for all $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$, in which case the equilibrium is unique with $\tau(c) = -\infty$ (full-disclosure). Because it cannot be the case that $\Delta(\tau; c) \leq 0$ for all τ , Definition 1(ii) rules out $\tau(c) = \infty$ (no-disclosure). \square

Proof of Lemma 2. Under normal updating,

$$\tilde{v} \mid x \sim N\left(a(s)x, b(s)^2\right), \quad \text{where } a(s) = \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} \quad \text{and } b(s) = \frac{\sigma s}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}},$$

so that $P(x) = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{v} \mid \tilde{v} \geq \tau, \tilde{x} = x] = a(s)x + b(s)\lambda\left(\frac{\tau - a(s)x}{b(s)}\right)$. For the marginal discloser $\tilde{v} = \tau$, we have $\tilde{x} = \tau + \tilde{\varepsilon} = \tau + s\tilde{Y}$ with $\tilde{Y} \sim N(0, 1)$. Taking expectations over \tilde{Y} ,

$$\mathbb{E}[P(x) \mid \tilde{v} = \tau] = a(s)\tau + b(s)\mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta_s(\tilde{Y}))], \quad (18)$$

where $\theta_s(y) \equiv \frac{\tau s / \sigma - \sigma y}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}}$. Differentiating inside the expectation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \mathbb{E}[P(x; c) \mid \tilde{v} = \tau] = a(s) + \frac{s^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta_s(\tilde{Y}))], \quad (19)$$

because $b(s)\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau}\theta_s(\tilde{Y}) = \frac{s^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2}$. Since $\lambda'(z) = \lambda(z)(\lambda(z) - z) \in (0, 1)$ for all z (Sampford, 1953) and $a(s) = \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} \in (0, 1)$, it follows that the derivative is in $(0, 1)$. \square

Proof of Lemma 3. The claim is shown in the proof of Lemma 1. \square

Proof of Proposition 1. Differentiating the non-disclosure price (from equation (17)),

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} P(\emptyset) = \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right), \quad \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \tau^2} P(\emptyset) = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \lambda''\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) < 0.$$

From lemma 2 and equation (19), $\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) \mid \tau] \in (0, 1)$ and

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \tau^2} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) \mid \tau] = \frac{s^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} \cdot \frac{s}{\sigma \sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta_s(\tilde{Y}))] > 0,$$

since the inverse Mill ratio is convex. Hence $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) \mid \tau]$ is strictly convex, while $P(\emptyset)$ is strictly concave. Therefore, $\Delta(\cdot; c)$ is strictly convex in τ . By lemma 3, $\Delta(\cdot; c)$ is strictly convex and diverges to ∞ at both tails: it has either no finite root, a unique tangency (i.e., a double root), or exactly two roots.

Further, strict convexity yields a unique minimizer τ^* of $\Delta(\cdot; c)$, characterized by the first-order condition $\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \Delta(\tau^*; c) = 0$. Moreover, $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow -\infty} \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \Delta(\tau; c) = a(s) - 1 < 0$ implies that τ^* is finite. We show next that $\tau^* < 0$ by evaluating $\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \Delta(\tau; c)$ at $\tau = 0$. First, for the non-disclosure price, $\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} P(\emptyset) \Big|_{\tau=0} = \lambda'(0) = \frac{2}{\pi}$. Second, for the disclosure expected payoff, let us define:

$$H(a) \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) \mid \tau] \Big|_{\tau=0} = a + (1 - a) \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})].$$

We need to show that $H'(a) > 0$ on $[0, 1]$, since it then immediately implies $H(a) > H(0) = \lambda'(0) = 2/\pi$ and so $\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \Delta(0; c) > 0$. To show this, we use Stein's lemma and the identity

$$\lambda'''(z) = (2\lambda(z) - z)\lambda''(z) + 2(\lambda'(z) - 1)\lambda'(z),$$

with $\lambda''(\cdot) > 0$ and $2\lambda(z) - z > 0$ (since $\lambda'(z) = \lambda(z)(\lambda(z) - z) > 0$). This implies:

$$\begin{aligned} H'(a) &= 1 - \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})] + \frac{1-a}{2} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'''(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})] \\ &\geq 1 - \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})] + (1-a) \mathbb{E}[(\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y}) - 1)\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})] \\ &\geq 1 - \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})] + (1-a) \left((\mathbb{E}[\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})])^2 - \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})] \right) \\ &= (1 - \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})]) (1 - (1-a) \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(-\sqrt{a} \tilde{Y})]) > 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from $0 < \lambda'(z) < 1$.

Then, $c_0 > 0$ is uniquely defined as $\Delta(\tau^*; c_0) = 0$, and the main claim in the Proposition follows immediately from noting that $\Delta(\tau^*; c) = 0$ has no solution (resp., two solutions) if $c < c_0$ ($c > c_0$), and a single solution $\tau(c_0) = \tau^*$ if $c = c_0$. Further $\Delta(\cdot; c)$ is strictly convex and minimized at $\tau^* < 0$, the two roots at $c > c_0$ must satisfy $\underline{\tau}(c) < \tau^* < \bar{\tau}(c)$. At either root $\tau(c)$, the implicit

function theorem yields

$$\tau'(c) = -\frac{\partial\Delta/\partial c}{\partial\Delta/\partial\tau} = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial}{\partial\tau}\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] - \frac{\partial}{\partial\tau}P(\emptyset)} = \frac{1}{\partial\Delta/\partial\tau}. \quad (20)$$

Since $\Delta(\cdot; c)$ is strictly convex, at the left (right) root, we have $\partial\Delta/\partial\tau < 0$ (resp. > 0). Hence $\underline{\tau}'(c) < 0 < \bar{\tau}'(c)$. The same implicit-function argument yields continuity of $\underline{\tau}(\cdot)$ and $\bar{\tau}(\cdot)$ in c for $c > c_0$ and, since $\lim_{|\tau| \rightarrow \infty} \Delta(\tau; c_0) = \infty$, it must be that $\underline{\tau}(c) \downarrow -\infty$ and $\bar{\tau}(c) \uparrow \infty$ as $c \rightarrow \infty$. \square

Proof of Corollary 1. Recall from Proposition 1 that c_0 is defined by $\Delta(\tau^*; c_0) = 0$ where τ^* is the first-order condition to $\Delta_\tau(\tau^*; \cdot) = 0$, i.e.,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial\tau}\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] \Big|_{\tau=\tau^*} = \frac{\partial}{\partial\tau}P(\emptyset) \Big|_{\tau=\tau^*},$$

which simplifies to

$$(1 - \rho^2) + \rho^2 \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] = \lambda'(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}). \quad (21)$$

Differentiating c_0 and applying the chain rule and the Envelope theorem yields, for ζ set to s or σ ,

$$\frac{dc_0}{d\zeta} = \frac{\partial}{\partial\zeta}\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] \Big|_{\tau=\tau^*}.$$

In what follows, to simplify notations, let us rewrite (18) as

$$\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] = (1 - \rho^2)\tau + \sigma\rho \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)].$$

Comparative statics in s . Differentiating,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial\rho}\mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] &= \mathbb{E}\left[\lambda'(\theta)\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial\rho}\right] = \frac{\tau}{\sigma}\mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] + \frac{\rho}{\sqrt{1-\rho^2}}\mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)\tilde{Y}] \\ &= \frac{\tau}{\sigma}\mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] - \rho\mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)], \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows, by Stein's lemma, from $\mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)\tilde{Y}] = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{d}{d\tilde{Y}}\lambda'(\theta)\right] = -\sqrt{1-\rho^2}\mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)]$.

implying that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] = \frac{\tau}{\sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] - \rho \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)].$$

Finally, using the above to differentiate (18),

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) \mid \tau] = \sigma \left(-2 \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} + \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] + \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] - \rho^2 \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)] \right). \quad (22)$$

Since $\theta = \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} - \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \tilde{Y}$ is linear in \tilde{Y} , Stein's lemma ($\mathbb{E}[\tilde{Y} f(\tilde{Y})] = \mathbb{E}[f'(\tilde{Y})]$) applied to $f(\tilde{Y}) = \lambda'(\theta(\tilde{Y}))$ yields

$$\mathbb{E}[\theta \lambda'(\theta)] = \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] + (1 - \rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)]. \quad (23)$$

The inverse Mills ratio satisfies $\lambda''(z) = (2\lambda(z) - z)\lambda'(z) - \lambda(z)$. Substituting into (23) returns

$$\rho^2 \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)] = \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] - \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] - \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)\lambda'(\theta)] + (1 - \rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)]. \quad (24)$$

Substituting (24) into (22) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) \mid \tau] &= -2 \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} + \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] + \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] - \rho^2 \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] - \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} - \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)\lambda'(\theta)] + \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] + (1 - \rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)]. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $(\lambda(\theta) - \theta)(1 - \lambda'(\theta)) = \lambda(\theta) - \theta - \lambda(\theta)\lambda'(\theta) + \theta\lambda'(\theta)$. Taking expectations and using $\mathbb{E}[\theta] = \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma}$ yields

$$\mathbb{E}[(1 - \lambda'(\theta))(\lambda(\theta) - \theta)] = \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] - \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} - \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)\lambda'(\theta)] + \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] + (1 - \rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)].$$

Comparing terms, we obtain the simplified form

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) \mid \tau] = 2\sigma \mathbb{E}[(1 - \lambda'(\theta))(\lambda(\theta) - \theta)]. \quad (25)$$

Since $0 < \lambda'(z) < 1$ and $\lambda(z) > z$ for all z , the integrand in (25) is strictly positive pointwise.

Hence $\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] > 0$. Given that $\frac{d\rho}{ds} = \frac{\sigma^2}{(\sigma^2 + s^2)^{3/2}} > 0$, the chain rule implies

$$\frac{dc_0}{ds} = \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] \Big|_{\tau=\tau^*} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] \Big|_{\tau=\tau^*} \frac{d\rho}{ds} > 0. \quad (26)$$

As $s \downarrow 0$, $\rho \rightarrow 0$ and $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] \rightarrow \tau$, hence

$$\lim_{s \downarrow 0} c_0 = \lim_{s \downarrow 0} (\tau^* - P(\emptyset)) = \inf_{\tau \in \mathbb{R}} (\tau - P(\emptyset)) = \inf_{\tau \in \mathbb{R}} (\tau + \sigma \lambda(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma})) = 0,$$

because $1 - \lambda'(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) > 0$.

Comparative statics in σ . From the same Envelope argument,

$$\frac{dc_0}{d\sigma} = \tau \frac{\partial a}{\partial \sigma} + \frac{\partial b}{\partial \sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] + b \frac{\partial}{\partial \sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] - \frac{\partial}{\partial \sigma} (-\sigma \lambda(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma})) \Big|_{\tau=\tau^*}.$$

Direct differentiation further yields:

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial \sigma} = \frac{2\sigma s^2}{(\sigma^2 + s^2)^2}, \quad \frac{\partial b}{\partial \sigma} = \frac{s^3}{(\sigma^2 + s^2)^{3/2}},$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] = \mathbb{E} \left[\lambda'(\theta) \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \sigma} \right], \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial \sigma} (-\sigma \lambda(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma})) = -\lambda(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \frac{\tau}{\sigma} \lambda'(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}).$$

We can then write

$$\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} \frac{\partial a}{\partial \sigma} = 2 \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} (1 - \rho^2) \rho^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial b}{\partial \sigma} \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] = \rho^3 \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)].$$

By $\theta = \rho \frac{\tau}{\sigma} - \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \tilde{Y}$, holding τ fixed,

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \sigma} = -\frac{\frac{\tau}{\sigma} \rho (2 - \rho^2)}{\sigma} - \frac{\rho^2 \sqrt{1 - \rho^2}}{\sigma} \tilde{Y}.$$

So that

$$b \mathbb{E} \left[\lambda'(\theta) \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \sigma} \right] = -\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} \rho^2 (2 - \rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] - \rho^3 \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta) \tilde{Y}].$$

By Stein's lemma,

$$\mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta) \tilde{Y}] = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{d}{d\tilde{Y}}\lambda'(\theta(Y))\right] = -\sqrt{1-\rho^2} \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)].$$

Then $b \mathbb{E}\left[\lambda'(\theta) \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \sigma}\right] = -\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} \rho^2 (2-\rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] + \rho^3 (1-\rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)]$. Adding the terms together,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dc_0}{d\sigma} &= 2\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} (1-\rho^2)\rho^2 + \rho^3 \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] - \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} \rho^2 (2-\rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] \\ &\quad + \rho^3 (1-\rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)] + \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right) + \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} \lambda'\left(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Using (21), this expression becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dc_0}{d\sigma} &= \underbrace{\left(\lambda\left(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right) + 2\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} - \lambda'\left(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right) \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right)}_{(i)} - \underbrace{\rho^4 \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} (2 - \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)])}_{(ii)} \\ &\quad + \underbrace{\rho^3 \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)]}_{(iii)} + \underbrace{\rho^3 (1-\rho^2) \mathbb{E}[\lambda''(\theta)]}_{(iv)}. \end{aligned}$$

Each bracketed term is strictly positive: (i) with $z = -\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} > 0$, this term is equal to $\lambda(z) - 2z + z\lambda'(z) = (\lambda(z) - z) - z + z\lambda'(z) > (\lambda(z) - z)\lambda'(z) - z + z\lambda'(z) = (\lambda(z) - z)^2 \lambda'(z) - z + z\lambda'(z) = (\lambda''(z) - \lambda(z)(\lambda'(z) - 1)) - z + z\lambda'(z) = \lambda''(z) + (\lambda(z) - z)(1 - \lambda'(z)) > 0$, where the inequalities follow from $\lambda'(z) < 1$, $\lambda(z) > z$, and strict convexity of $\lambda(z)$; (ii) $\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} < 0$, $\rho \in (0, 1)$, and $0 < \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\theta)] < 1$ imply (ii) > 0 ; (iii) $\lambda > 0$ implies (iii) > 0 ; (iv) $\lambda'' > 0$ and $\rho \in (0, 1)$ imply (iv) > 0 .

Finally, if $\sigma \downarrow 0$, $\rho \rightarrow 1$, so that

$$\lim_{\sigma \downarrow 0} c_0(\sigma) = \liminf_{\tau \in \mathbb{R}} \sigma \left(\lambda\left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) + \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) \right) = \lim_{\sigma \downarrow 0} 2\sigma \lambda(0) = \lim_{\sigma \downarrow 0} 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sigma = 0. \quad \square$$

Proof of Corollary 2. Suppose that $c > c_0$, so that there are two subgame equilibria $\underline{\tau}$ and $\bar{\tau}$.

Comparative statics in s . In equation (26), we proved that

$$0 < \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) \mid \tau] = \frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial s}.$$

Therefore Δ is increasing in s . Recall from what the proof following (20) that $\frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial \tau} \Big|_{\tau=\underline{\tau}} < 0$ and $\frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial \tau} \Big|_{\tau=\bar{\tau}} > 0$. It is then readily verified from the implicit function theorem that

$$\frac{d\tau}{ds} \Big|_{\tau=\bar{\tau}} < 0 < \frac{d\tau}{ds} \Big|_{\tau=\underline{\tau}}.$$

Comparative statics in σ . First, we study the comparative statics for $\underline{\tau}$ (which is known to be negative from $\underline{\tau}(c) \leq \tau(c_0) < 0$ in Corollary 1) when $\sigma \downarrow 0$. Then, both $a(s)$ and $b(s)$ converge to zero in Lemma 2 and, moreover, $\theta_s(y) \rightarrow -\infty$, which in turn implies that

$$\mathbb{E} [P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] = a(s) \tau + b(s) \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta_s(\tilde{Y}))] \rightarrow 0.$$

Finally, for the non-disclosure price, an expansion of the Mills ratio yields:

$$P(\emptyset) = \sigma \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) = \sigma \left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma} + \left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right)^{-1} + o\left(\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right)^{-1}\right)\right) \rightarrow -\tau.$$

Defining $\Delta(\tau; c, 0) = \lim_{\sigma \downarrow 0} \Delta(\tau; c, \sigma) = -c - \tau$. Then $\Delta(\cdot; c, 0)$ has a unique root at $\underline{\tau}(c) = -c$, which implies a probability of disclosure $1 - \Phi\left(\frac{\tau(c)}{\sigma}\right) \sim \Phi\left(\frac{c}{\sigma}\right) \rightarrow 1$, which decreases for σ sufficiently small.

Second, for $\bar{\tau}$, we have shown in the proof of corollary 1 that Δ is increasing in σ (because the average upper truncation $\mathbb{E}(P(\tau + \varepsilon))$ is increasing in σ while the lower truncation $P(\emptyset)$ is decreasing in σ), implying that $\bar{\tau}(c)$ is decreasing in σ . Hence, if $\bar{\tau}(c) > 0$, $\bar{\tau}(c)/\sigma$ is decreasing, which implies that the probability of disclosure $1 - \Phi(\bar{\tau}(c)/\sigma)$ is increasing. Note also that, if $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$, the probability of disclosure converges to one when $s = 0$ (Verrecchia 1990), and it has been shown earlier to be greater with $s > 0$, so it must also converge to one for any $s > 0$. \square

Proof of Proposition 2. Suppose that $c \in [0, \bar{c}]$.

Case (i). If $\bar{c} < c_0$, $\tau(c) = -\infty$ features unravelling for any c , so that the certifier's profit $V(c) = c$ is increasing in c and maximized at \bar{c} .

Case (ii). If $\bar{c} \in [c_0, \underline{V}^{-1}(c_0))$, $\text{Sup}_{c < c_0} V(c) = c_0$; in other words, there exists a fee c triggering unravelling that can attain a profit arbitrarily close to \bar{c} . Further, any $c \geq c_0$ yields a profit

$$V(c) < \bar{V}(c) \leq \bar{V}(\bar{c}) < c_0,$$

contradicting the optimality of any $c \geq c_0$. Since there is not fee achieving $V(c) = c_0$, the certifier's problem has no solution.

Case (iii). If $\bar{c} \geq \underline{V}^{-1}(c_0)$, we know from case (ii) that any solution must satisfy $V(c^*) \geq c_0$. If $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(c^*)$, since $\underline{V}(c)$ is increasing, it must hold that $\tau(c) = \underline{\tau}(c)$ for any $c \in (c^*, \bar{c}]$ (case (iii.a)). If $\tau(c^*) = \bar{\tau}(c^*)$, using the fact that $\underline{V}(c) > \bar{V}(c)$, it must hold that $\tau(c) = \bar{\tau}(c)$ for any $c \in (c^*, \bar{c}]$ (case (iii.b)). \square

Proof of Corollary 3. If (11) holds, then $\bar{V}(c)$ is decreasing on $[c_0, \infty)$, which implies that, in case (iii.b), $\bar{V}(c^*) = c_0(1 - F(\bar{\tau}(c^*))) < c_0$ cannot be an optimal fee. If (11) does not hold, the optimal fee attains $\bar{V}(c^*) = \bar{V}^{**}$. \square

Profit of Lemma 4. Suppose $c > c_0$. We first show (11). By the implicit function theorem,

$$\bar{V}'(c) = 1 - \Phi(\bar{\tau}/\sigma) - \frac{c}{\sigma} \phi(\bar{\tau}/\sigma) \bar{\tau}'(c), \quad \bar{\tau}'(c) = \frac{1}{\frac{\partial \Delta(\tau, c)}{\partial \tau} \Big|_{\tau=\bar{\tau}}}.$$

On the upper root, we know that $\bar{\tau}'(c) > 0$. Then, from $1 - \Phi(\bar{\tau}/\sigma) = \phi(\bar{\tau}/\sigma)/\lambda(\bar{\tau}/\sigma)$,

$$V'(c) = \frac{\phi(\bar{\tau}/\sigma)}{\lambda(\bar{\tau}/\sigma)} \left[1 - \frac{c}{\sigma} \frac{\lambda(\bar{\tau}/\sigma)}{\frac{\partial \Delta(\tau, c)}{\partial \tau} \Big|_{\tau=\bar{\tau}}} \right]. \quad (27)$$

The sign of $V'(c)$ is the sign of the bracket. Because $\bar{\tau}(c)/\sigma \geq \bar{\tau}(c_0)/\sigma$ and λ is increasing,

$$\frac{c}{\sigma} \frac{\lambda(\bar{\tau}/\sigma)}{\frac{\partial \Delta(\tau, c)}{\partial \tau} \Big|_{\tau=\bar{\tau}}} \geq \frac{c_0}{\sigma} \frac{\lambda(\bar{\tau}(c_0)/\sigma)}{\sup_{c \geq c_0} \frac{\partial \Delta(\tau, c)}{\partial \tau} \Big|_{\tau=\bar{\tau}}}.$$

Given that $0 < \lambda'(\cdot) < 1$,

$$\frac{\partial \Delta(\tau, c)}{\partial \tau} \Big|_{\tau=\bar{\tau}} = a + (1 - a) \mathbb{E}[\lambda'(\cdot)] - \lambda'(-\bar{\tau}(c)/\sigma) \leq a + (1 - a) \cdot 1 = 1,$$

where a is from lemma 2 (omitting the dependence on s to simplify notations). This implies condition (11) in the lemma.

Now we prove that the profit of the certifier tends to zero when considering $\bar{\tau} \rightarrow \infty$ for c sufficiently large. Recall the indifference condition

$$\underbrace{\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) \mid \tau]}_{=a(s)\tau + b(s)\mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta_s(\tilde{Y}))]} - c = P(\emptyset; \tau) = -\sigma \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right). \quad (28)$$

As $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, $\theta_s(\tilde{Y}) = \frac{s}{\sigma\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}}\tau + O(1)$, and since $\lambda(x)/x \rightarrow 1$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta_s(\tilde{Y}))] = \frac{s}{\sigma\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}}\tau + o(\tau),$$

implying that

$$\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) \mid \tau] = \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} + \frac{s^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2}\right)\tau + o(\tau) = \tau + o(\tau). \quad (29)$$

Moreover, $\lambda(-x) \rightarrow 0$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$, so

$$P(\emptyset; \tau) = -\sigma \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) = o(\tau). \quad (30)$$

It then follows from the indifference condition jointly with (29)–(30) that $\bar{\tau}(c) \sim c$, implying that $\bar{V}(c) \sim c(1 - \Phi(c/\sigma))$, where this term is known to converge from the zero from the fact that the normal has a sub-exponential upper tail. \square

Proof of Lemma 5. From lemma 4, the profit $\bar{V}(c)$ converges to zero if c is sufficiently large, therefore, there exists c' such that $\bar{V}(c') < V(c_0)$ for any $c \geq c'$. It follows by continuity that $\bar{V}(c)$ attains its maximum on the compact set $[c_0, c']$. \square

Proof of Proposition 3. From Corollary 3, (11) implies that $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(c^*)$ and therefore, from proposition 2, for any $c \in (c^*, \bar{c}]$, $\tau(c) = \bar{\tau}(c)$. If $c^* < \bar{c}$, this implies that $\tau(c)$ is discontinuous at c^* even though the subgame equilibrium is not unique at c^* , a contradiction to (C). \square

Proof of Proposition 4. Given that the proof is long and cumbersome, and a formalization of the argument in text, it is given in a supplementary appendix. \square

Proof of Proposition 5. If $c < c_0 = \min \psi$, then $\psi(\tau) > c$ for every interior τ . Hence the marginal discloser strictly prefers disclosure at every interior threshold and the unique equilibrium is full disclosure. If $c \in [c_0, c_1]$, continuity of ψ on $[\underline{v}, \bar{v}]$ and the intermediate value theorem imply that there exists at least one τ^* with $\psi(\tau^*) = c$, where τ^* is a subgame equilibrium threshold. If $c > c_1 = \max \psi$, then $\psi(\tau) < c$ for every interior τ . Thus the marginal discloser strictly prefers non-disclosure at every interior threshold, and the unique equilibrium is no disclosure.

For part (iv), suppose τ_0 is a strict local minimizer and $c \in (\psi(\tau_0), \min\{\psi(\underline{v}), \psi(\bar{v})\})$. By strict local minimality, there exists $\delta > 0$ such that $\psi(\tau) > \psi(\tau_0)$ for all $\tau \in (\tau_0 - \delta, \tau_0 + \delta) \setminus \{\tau_0\}$. Because $c > \psi(\tau_0)$ and $c < \psi(\underline{v})$, continuity of ψ yields at least one solution on the interval (\underline{v}, τ_0) . Likewise, because $c < \psi(\bar{v})$, continuity yields at least one solution on (τ_0, \bar{v}) . Denote any such solutions by $\underline{\tau}(c)$ and $\bar{\tau}(c)$, which satisfy $\underline{\tau}(c) < \tau_0 < \bar{\tau}(c)$ and $\psi(\underline{\tau}(c)) = \psi(\bar{\tau}(c)) = c$. Hence there are at least two distinct equilibrium thresholds. \square

Proof of Corollary 4. In the noiseless benchmark, the marginal type τ receives price τ upon disclosure, so the net disclosure benefit is $\psi^0(\tau) \equiv \tau - \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} < \tau)$. As $\tau \downarrow \underline{v}$, $\mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} < \tau)$ converges to \underline{v} . It follows that $\lim_{\tau \downarrow \underline{v}} \psi^0(\tau) = \lim_{\tau \downarrow \underline{v}} (\tau - \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} < \tau)) = \underline{v} - \underline{v} = 0$. So the threshold type's disclosure benefit is arbitrarily small near full disclosure. Hence, no strictly positive cost can sustain full disclosure, i.e., $c_0^0 = 0$. By contrast, Proposition 5 implies that in the noisy model, the unraveling cutoff satisfies $c_0^s > 0$. Therefore, the maximal cost sustaining full disclosure is strictly higher in the noisy disclosure model than in the noiseless benchmark. \square

Proof of Proposition 6. Let $\underline{\tau}(c) \equiv \sup\{\tau \in [\underline{v}, \tau_0) : \psi(\tau) = c\}$ and $\bar{\tau}(c) \equiv \inf\{\tau \in (\tau_0, \bar{v}] : \psi(\tau) = c\}$. The existence of $\underline{\tau}(c)$ and $\bar{\tau}(c)$ follows directly from Proposition 5. Take $\psi(\tau_0) < c < c' < \min\{\psi(\bar{v}), \psi(\underline{v})\}$. Because $\psi(\underline{\tau}(c')) = c' > c > \psi(\tau_0)$, there is at least one solution to $\psi(\tau) = c$ in $(\underline{\tau}(c'), \tau_0)$ by the intermediate value theorem. Then the closest such solution to the left of τ_0 must satisfy $\underline{\tau}(c') < \underline{\tau}(c)$. Similarly, because $\psi(\tau_0) < c < c' = \psi(\bar{\tau}(c'))$, there is at least one solution to $\psi(\tau) = c$ in $(\tau_0, \bar{\tau}(c'))$. Then the closest solution to the right of τ_0 satisfies $\bar{\tau}(c') > \bar{\tau}(c)$. It follows that $\underline{\tau}(c') < \underline{\tau}(c) < \tau_0 < \bar{\tau}(c) < \bar{\tau}(c')$, which proves the result. \square

Proof of Proposition 7. We know from the proof of corollary 1 that $\mathbb{E}P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})$ is (strictly) increasing in s . This implies the following:

(i) From the fact that $P(\emptyset) < \tau$ for any $\tau > \tau(0)$ (Acharya et al. 2011), it must also be true that $P(\emptyset) < \tau < \mathbb{E}P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})$ for any $s > 0$. Therefore, there is no equilibrium with $\tau \geq \tau(0)$.

(ii) We also similarly know that $P(\emptyset)$ is decreasing in τ for $\tau < \tau(0)$, so that it can intersect at most once with the (increasing) $\mathbb{E}P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})$. The existence of this unique solution then follows from the intermediate value theorem because (ii.a) $\mathbb{E}P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) \rightarrow -\infty$ as $\tau \rightarrow -\infty$ and (ii.b) at $\tau = \tau(0)$, $\mathbb{E}P(\tau(0) + \tilde{\varepsilon}) > \tau(0) = P(\emptyset)$.

The comparative statics in s follows immediately from the monotonicity of $\mathbb{E}P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})$, while the comparative statics in σ can be verified by factoring all expectations in the indifference condition by σ , so that the standardized threshold τ/σ is solely a function of s/σ , i.e.,

$$\frac{1}{\sigma} \left[a(s) \frac{\tau}{\sigma} + b(s) \mathbb{E}(\lambda(\theta_s(Y))) \right] + \frac{(1-q)\phi(\tau/\sigma)}{q + (1-q)\Phi(\tau/\sigma)} = 0, \quad (31)$$

implying that the probability of disclosure $(1-q)(1-\Phi(s/\sigma))$ is decreasing in σ . \square

Proof of Lemma 6. We show first that $P(\cdot)$ is convex. By the chain rule,

$$P'(x) = a(s) + b(s) \lambda' \left(\frac{\tau - a(s)x}{b(s)} \right) \cdot \frac{-a(s)}{b(s)} = a(s) \left(1 - \lambda' \left(\frac{\tau - a(s)x}{b(s)} \right) \right).$$

Differentiating once more,

$$P''(x) = a(s) \left(-\lambda'' \left(\frac{\tau - a(s)x}{b(s)} \right) \cdot \frac{-a(s)}{b(s)} \right) = \frac{a(s)^2}{b(s)} \lambda'' \left(\frac{\tau - a(s)x}{b(s)} \right).$$

Given that $\lambda''(\cdot) > 0$, $P(x)$ is strictly convex in x . If $\epsilon \sim N(0, s)$ and $\epsilon' \sim N(0, s')$, $s > s'$ implies that ϵ is a mean-preserving spread of ϵ' . Hence, from Jensen's inequality, $\mathbb{E}_\epsilon P(v + \epsilon' | \hat{s}) < \mathbb{E}_\epsilon P(v + \epsilon | \hat{s})$, implying the stated result that the firm prefers more noise. \square

Proof of Lemma 7. Using properties of truncated normal distributions,

$$\begin{aligned} D(\tau) &= \sigma \left[\lambda \left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma} \right) + \lambda \left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma} \right) \right] \\ D'(\tau) &= \lambda' \left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma} \right) - \lambda' \left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma} \right), \end{aligned}$$

so that $D'(\cdot)$ has the sign of τ . Thus D is strictly decreasing on $(-\infty, 0)$ and strictly increasing on $(0, \infty)$, with a unique minimum at $\tau = 0$ achieving $D(0) = \frac{4\sigma}{\sqrt{2\pi}}$. Finally, for $\tau > 0$, $\mathbb{E}[v | v \geq \tau] \geq \tau$ and $\mathbb{E}[v | v < \tau] \geq \mathbb{E}[v | v < 0] = -2\sigma/\sqrt{2\pi}$, hence $D(\tau) \geq \tau + \frac{2\sigma}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \rightarrow \infty$ as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$. \square

Proof of Proposition 9. We have shown in text that an equilibrium cannot involve $c \leq c_0$. Suppose by contradiction that $\bar{\tau}(c^*)$ occurs in an equilibrium. It must then hold that $\bar{\tau}(c)$ is the subgame for *all* $c > c_0$ since any $\underline{\tau}(c)$ yields a higher probability of disclosure than any $\bar{\tau}(c)$. But this immediately implies that $c^* = c_0$, by monotonicity of $\bar{\Pi}(c)$, which contradicts our earlier observation that $c^* > c_0$.

We have therefore shown that $\tau(c^*) = \underline{\tau}(c^*)$; further, because $\underline{\tau}(c)$ is increasing in c , c^* optimal requires that $\tau(c) = \bar{\tau}(c)$ for all $c > c^*$ to prevent a profitable increase in the fee. To show sufficiency, we are left to verify that some $c \uparrow c_0$, arbitrarily close to c_0 and which implies unravelling does not achieve more profit than c^* . Comparing both profits, $c^*(1 - \Phi(\frac{\bar{\tau}(c^*)}{\sigma})) \geq c_0$. From (15), this equation simplifies to the stated equation in the proposition. \square

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Supplementary Online Appendix

In this appendix, we use $\lambda(z) \equiv \phi(z)/(1 - \Phi(z))$ as the inverse Mill's ratio, with $\phi(z)$ (resp., $\Phi(z)$) indicating the pdf (resp., cdf) of the standard normal distribution. In parts of the proof, we also simplify notations using $\rho \equiv \frac{s}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \in (0, 1)$, $\theta_s(y) \equiv \frac{\tau s / \sigma - \sigma y}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} = \frac{\tau \rho}{\sigma} - y \sqrt{1 - \rho^2}$, and $\theta \equiv \theta_s(\tilde{Y})$, with \tilde{Y} defined as a standard normal random variable.

Additional Proofs from Section 3

Lemma 8. *Let two subgame equilibria be equivalent if they prescribe the same disclosure choices almost surely. Then, any subgame equilibrium is equivalent to a threshold equilibrium, i.e., such that the firm discloses if and only if $v \geq \tau$.*

Proof of Lemma 8. The statement is obvious for full-disclosure or non-disclosure (setting $|\tau| = \infty$). For any disclosure set A with non-zero probability, define

$$P(x; c) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} \in A, \tilde{x} = x), \quad P(\emptyset; c) = \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} \notin A).$$

Since $\tilde{x} | \tilde{v} \sim N(\tilde{v}, s^2)$, the conditional densities $\{f(x|v)\}_v$ form a location family with the monotone likelihood ratio property (MLRP) in x : if $v_1 > v_2$, then $f(x|v_1)/f(x|v_2)$ increases in x . By Bayes' rule, this property carries over to the posterior. Hence, under the A , the pricing function $P(x; c)$ is strictly increasing in x . This, in turn, shows that if $v \in A$, i.e.,

$$\Delta(v) \equiv \mathbb{E}_x [P(x; c) | v] - c - P(\emptyset; c) \geq 0,$$

then, for any $v' > v$, $\Delta(v') > \Delta(v)$ so that the $v' \in A$. □

Proposition 10. *As σ or s become large, c_0 converges to a finite limit.*

Proof of Proposition 10. As $s \uparrow \infty$, $\rho \rightarrow 1$ and $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) \mid \tau] \rightarrow \sigma \lambda(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})$, so

$$c_\infty^s(\sigma) \equiv \lim_{s \uparrow \infty} c_0 = \inf_{\tau \in \mathbb{R}} \sigma \left(\lambda\left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) + \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma}\right) \right) = 2\sigma \lambda(0) = 2\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sigma.$$

As $\sigma \uparrow \infty$, $\rho \rightarrow 0$, so that (21) simplifies to

$$1 - \lambda'\left(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right) = \rho^2 \left(1 - \mathbb{E} \left[\lambda'\left(\rho \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} - \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \tilde{Y}\right) \right] \right). \quad (32)$$

Asymptotics for the inverse Mills ratio imply

$$1 - \lambda'(z) = \text{Var}(X \mid X > z) \sim z^{-2} \quad (z \rightarrow \infty),$$

so because $\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} \rightarrow -\infty$,

$$1 - \lambda'\left(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right) \sim \left(\frac{\sigma}{\tau^*}\right)^2,$$

which multiplying both sides of (32) by $\left(\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right)^2$ yields

$$\left(\rho \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right)^2 \left(1 - \mathbb{E} \left[\lambda'\left(\rho \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} - \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \tilde{Y}\right) \right] \right) \rightarrow 1.$$

Since $\rho \downarrow 0$ and $\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} \rightarrow -\infty$, the term $-\rho \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}$ converges to a finite positive constant k as $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$, which, from (32), satisfies the following fixed point. Next, to compute the limit of c_0 , we decompose

$$c_0 = \left(\sigma \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} + \sigma \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right) \right) - \sigma \rho^2 \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} + \sigma \rho \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)].$$

Using the inverse Mills' expansion $\lambda(z) = z + z^{-1} + o(z^{-1})$ as $z \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$\sigma \left(\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} + \lambda\left(-\frac{\tau^*}{\sigma}\right) \right) = \sigma \left(-\frac{\sigma}{\tau^*} + o\left(\frac{\sigma}{|\tau^*|}\right) \right) \rightarrow \frac{s}{k},$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} -\sigma \rho^2 \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} &= -(\sigma \rho) \left(\rho \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} \right) \rightarrow sk \\ \sigma \rho \mathbb{E} \left[\lambda \left(\rho \frac{\tau^*}{\sigma} - \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \tilde{Y} \right) \right] &\rightarrow s \mathbb{E}[\lambda(-\tilde{Y} - k)]. \end{aligned}$$

And it follows that

$$c_\infty^\sigma(s) \equiv \lim_{\sigma \uparrow \infty} c_0 = s \left(k + \frac{1}{k} + \mathbb{E}[\lambda(-\tilde{Y} - k)] \right). \quad (33)$$

□

Proposition 11. *There exists a critical value $c_\infty^\sigma(s)$ given by (33) such that, for σ sufficiently large, the probability of disclosure is equal to one and, otherwise, the probability of disclosure is strictly increasing.*

Proof of Proposition 11. Along the lower equilibrium, $\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)/\sigma \rightarrow -\infty$ as $\sigma \uparrow \infty$. Thus, with $\tau = \underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)$,

$$-\frac{\tau}{\sigma} \rightarrow +\infty, \quad \sigma \lambda \left(-\frac{\tau}{\sigma} \right) = -\tau - \frac{\sigma^2}{\tau} + o\left(\frac{\sigma^2}{\tau}\right) \quad (\sigma \uparrow \infty),$$

by the inverse–Mills expansion.

Next,

$$\frac{\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)}{\sigma^2} \rightarrow -\frac{1}{c - s \mathbb{E}[\lambda(-\tilde{Y})]} < 0 \quad (\sigma \uparrow \infty).$$

Consequently,

$$\frac{\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)}{\sigma} \sim -\frac{\sigma}{c - s \mathbb{E}[\lambda(-\tilde{Y})]} \rightarrow -\infty.$$

Thus

$$1 - \Phi\left(\frac{\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)}{\sigma}\right) \rightarrow 1 \quad (\sigma \uparrow \infty).$$

Moreover, from

$$\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma) = -\frac{\sigma^2}{c - s \mathbb{E}[\lambda(-\tilde{Y})]} + o(\sigma^2),$$

we obtain

$$\partial \underline{\tau}(c, \sigma) / \partial \sigma = -\frac{2\sigma}{c - s \mathbb{E}[\lambda(-\tilde{Y})]} + o(\sigma),$$

and hence

$$\frac{d}{d\sigma} \left(\frac{\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)}{\sigma} \right) = \frac{\sigma \partial \underline{\tau}(c, \sigma) / \partial \sigma - \underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)}{\sigma^2} \rightarrow -\frac{1}{c - s \mathbb{E}[\lambda(-\tilde{Y})]} < 0 \quad (\sigma \uparrow \infty).$$

Therefore, for all σ large enough,

$$\frac{d}{d\sigma} \left(\frac{\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)}{\sigma} \right) < 0,$$

and again the derivative of the probability of disclosure is

$$-\phi \left(\frac{\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)}{\sigma} \right) \frac{d}{d\sigma} \left(\frac{\underline{\tau}(c, \sigma)}{\sigma} \right) > 0 \quad \text{for } \sigma \text{ large.}$$

□

Proposition 12. *If $\rho > 1/\sqrt{2}$ (i.e., $\sigma < s$), the probability of disclosure is decreasing in σ .*

Proof of Proposition 12. In what follows, we write $z(\sigma) \equiv \bar{\tau}/\sigma$ and make the dependence of the variables on σ explicit when needed for clarity. By lemma 2, the indifference condition can be written as

$$\sigma H(z(\sigma), \rho(\sigma)) = c, \tag{34}$$

where $H(z, \rho) \equiv (1 - \rho^2)z + \rho \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta)] + \lambda(-z)$. Differentiating the above expression,

$$0 = \frac{d}{d\sigma} [\sigma H(z(\sigma), \rho(\sigma))] = H + \sigma (H_z z'(\sigma) + H_\rho \rho'(\sigma)).$$

Substituting $\rho'(\sigma) = -\frac{\rho(\sigma)(1-\rho(\sigma)^2)}{\sigma}$ into the above expression and reorganizing terms:

$$z'(\sigma) = -\frac{H(z, \rho) - \rho(1 - \rho^2)H_\rho(z, \rho)}{\sigma H_z(z, \rho)}. \tag{35}$$

We use the following auxiliary lemma.

Lemma 9. $0 < H_\rho(z, \rho) < 2 \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\theta) - \theta]$.

Proof of Lemma 9. Because $H(z, \rho) = \frac{1}{\sigma} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon}) | \tau] + \lambda(-z)$,

$$H_\rho(z, \rho) = 2 \mathbb{E} \left[(1 - \lambda'(\theta))(\lambda(\theta) - \theta) \right]. \quad (36)$$

Using the fact that $0 < \lambda'(u) < 1$ and $\lambda(u) > u$, each factor in the expectation is strictly positive and therefore $H_\rho(z, \rho) > 0$. Moreover, since $0 < 1 - \lambda'(\theta) < 1$, completing the proof. \square

Recall from Proposition 1 that, at the upper threshold, $H_z(z(\sigma), \rho(\sigma)) = \frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial \tau} \Big|_{\tau=\bar{\tau}(\sigma)} > 0$. Therefore the sign of $z'(\sigma)$ is the opposite of the sign of

$$N(z, \rho) \equiv H(z, \rho) - \rho(1 - \rho^2)H_\rho(z, \rho) > z + \lambda(-z),$$

where the last inequality follows from $\rho \geq 1/\sqrt{2}$ and lemma 9. To prove $z'(\sigma) < 0$, one needs to show that $N(z, \rho) > 0$, i.e., the right-most term is positive, which is implied from $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{Y} | \tilde{Y} < z] = -\frac{\phi(z)}{\Phi(z)} = -\lambda(-z)$. \square

Additional Proofs from Section 4

Proposition 13. *Suppose that $\bar{c} < \underline{V}^{-1}(c_0)$ and denote c^* the optimal fee chosen by the certifier:*

- (i) *If $\bar{c} < c_0$, the certifier chooses $c^* = \bar{c}$ and achieves full-disclosure and profit \bar{c} ;*
- (ii) *If $\bar{c} \in [c_0, \underline{V}^{-1}(c_0))$, there exists no equilibrium;*

Proof of Proposition 13. *Case (i).* If $\bar{c} < c_0$, $\tau(c) = -\infty$ features unravelling for any c , so that the certifier's profit $V(c) = c$ is increasing in c and maximized at \bar{c} .

Case (ii). If $\bar{c} \in [c_0, \underline{V}^{-1}(c_0))$, $\text{Sup}_{c < c_0} V(c) = c_0$; in other words, there exists a fee c triggering unravelling that can attain a profit arbitrarily close to \bar{c} . Further, any $c \geq c_0$ yields a profit

$$V(c) < \bar{V}(c) \leq \bar{V}(\bar{c}) < c_0,$$

contradicting the optimality of any $c \geq c_0$. Since there is not fee achieving $V(c) = c_0$, the certifier's problem has no solution. \square

Next, we provide a simple robustness foundation for Assumption (C). Fix a compact interval $I \subset \text{int}(C)$. For each $c \in I$, Proposition 1 implies that the disclosure subgame admits two equilibrium thresholds, $\underline{\tau}(c)$ and $\bar{\tau}(c)$, both continuous in c .

Suppose that after the certifier chooses a fee $c \in I$, investors observe $\hat{c} = c + v_\eta$, where v_η is payoff-irrelevant noise with mean zero and $v_\eta \rightarrow 0$ in probability as $\eta \downarrow 0$. For each $\eta > 0$ and observed fee \hat{c} , let $\mu_\eta(\hat{c})$ denote investors' continuation belief about the disclosure threshold that will be played in the disclosure subgame. In a pure perturbed equilibrium, consistency requires that the threshold actually played coincide with the threshold investors conjecture. Let $\tau_\eta(\hat{c})$ denote the selected threshold in the perturbed game. Then $\tau_\eta(\hat{c}) = \mu_\eta(\hat{c})$ in equilibrium.

We impose the following regularity condition on perturbed beliefs: the family $\{\mu_\eta\}_{\eta>0}$ is locally equicontinuous on I , i.e., for every $\zeta > 0$, there exists $\delta > 0$ such that, for all sufficiently small η ,

$$|\mu_\eta(c) - \mu_\eta(c')| < \zeta \quad \text{whenever } c, c' \in I \text{ and } |c - c'| < \delta.$$

This condition implies that nearby observed fees generate nearby continuation beliefs, uniformly as the observation noise becomes small. It rules out arbitrarily steep belief switching across arbitrarily close cost realizations.

Proposition 14. *Suppose that, along some sequence $\eta_n \downarrow 0$, the perturbed thresholds satisfy $\tau_{\eta_n}(c) \rightarrow \tau(c)$ for every $c \in I$, where the limit $\tau(c) \in \{\underline{\tau}(c), \bar{\tau}(c)\}$. Then τ is continuous on I . Moreover, τ cannot switch between $\underline{\tau}$ and $\bar{\tau}$ and must coincide with one of the sequences.*

Proof of Proposition 14. Because $\tau_\eta(\hat{c}) = \mu_\eta(\hat{c})$ in any pure perturbed equilibrium, the family $\{\tau_\eta\}_{\eta>0}$ is locally equicontinuous on I .

We first prove continuity of τ . Fix an arbitrary $c \in I$ and $\zeta > 0$. By local equicontinuity, there

exists $\delta > 0$ such that, for all sufficiently small η ,

$$|\tau_\eta(c') - \tau_\eta(c)| < \zeta/3 \quad \text{for any } c' \in I \text{ and } |c' - c| < \delta.$$

Now fix such c' with $|c' - c| < \delta$. Since $\tau_{\eta_n}(c) \rightarrow \tau(c)$ and $\tau_{\eta_n}(c') \rightarrow \tau(c')$, there exists $N(c')$ such that for all $n \geq N(c')$, $|\tau_{\eta_n}(c) - \tau(c)| < \zeta/3$ and $|\tau_{\eta_n}(c') - \tau(c')| < \zeta/3$. So for all $n \geq N(c')$,

$$|\tau(c') - \tau(c)| \leq |\tau(c') - \tau_{\eta_n}(c')| + |\tau_{\eta_n}(c') - \tau_{\eta_n}(c)| + |\tau_{\eta_n}(c) - \tau(c)| < \zeta.$$

Therefore, τ is continuous at c and continuous on I .

Let $r(c) \equiv \frac{\tau(c) - \underline{\tau}(c)}{\bar{\tau}(c) - \underline{\tau}(c)}$. Because $I \subset \text{int}(C)$, the two sequences $\underline{\tau}$ and $\bar{\tau}$ are distinct on I and $\bar{\tau}(c) - \underline{\tau}(c) > 0$ for all $c \in I$. Since $\underline{\tau}$, $\bar{\tau}$, and τ are all continuous in c , $r(c)$ is continuous. Because $\tau(c) \in \{\underline{\tau}(c), \bar{\tau}(c)\}$, we have $r(c) \in \{0, 1\}$ for every $c \in I$. A continuous function from an interval to the set $\{0, 1\}$ must be constant. Hence r is constant on I and τ coincides either with $\underline{\tau}$ everywhere on I or with $\bar{\tau}$ everywhere on I . \square

Proposition 15. *If off-equilibrium beliefs must satisfy the requirement in Govindan and Wilson (2009) and Man (2012), the forward induction equilibrium is unique with $c^* = \bar{c}$.*

Proof of Proposition 15. Consider a subgame equilibrium. Let $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ be investors' posterior that the disclosure threshold is $\underline{\tau}(\bar{c})$ and $1 - \alpha$ be the posterior that the disclosure threshold is $\bar{\tau}(\bar{c})$ at their information set conditional on observing \bar{c} and non-disclosure. If the certifier had chosen \bar{c} , then the equilibrium continuation payoff is $\alpha \underline{V}(\bar{c}) + (1 - \alpha) \bar{V}(\bar{c})$. But the payoff for the certifier by choosing c_2 is at least $\bar{V}(c_2)$. So \bar{c} is (weakly) optimal for the certifier if and only if

$$\alpha \geq \frac{\bar{V}(c_2) - \bar{V}(\bar{c})}{\underline{V}(\bar{c}) - \bar{V}(\bar{c})}.$$

We use Man (2012)'s notion of normal form forward induction based on limits of ε -perfect equilibria and her iterative relevance construction of F^k and R^k (a slight adjustment yields the same

result under the formalization of Govindan and Wilson (2009)). Let σ^* be a normal form perfect equilibrium and $\Sigma^*(\sigma^*)$ be the set of normal form perfect equilibria that induce the same outcome as σ^* . A pure strategy s_i is (first-order) relevant for $\Sigma^*(\sigma^*)$ if there exists a sequence of ε -perfect equilibria $\{\sigma^n\}$ with $\sigma^n \rightarrow \sigma$ for some $\sigma \in \Sigma^*(\sigma^*)$ such that s_i is a best reply to σ_{-i}^n for all n . A normal form perfect equilibrium σ^* is a first-order forward induction equilibrium if there exists a sequence of ε -perfect equilibria $\{\sigma^n\}$ converging to σ^* such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sigma^n(s')}{\sigma^n(s)} = 0$$

whenever s contains only first-order relevant strategies and s' contains at least one irrelevant strategy. Higher-order iterated relevance and the forward induction equilibrium are defined as follows. Let $F^0(\sigma^*) = \Sigma^*(\sigma^*)$ and $R_i^1(\sigma^*)$ be player i 's set of first-order relevant strategies and $R^1(\sigma^*) = \prod_i R_i^1(\sigma^*)$. Recursively, for $k \geq 1$:

$$F^k(\sigma^*) = \left\{ \sigma \in F^{k-1}(\sigma^*) \mid \exists \varepsilon\text{-perfect equilibria } \{\sigma^n\} \rightarrow \sigma \text{ such that for all } \ell = 1, \dots, k, \right. \\ \left. \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sigma^n(s')}{\sigma^n(s)} = 0 \text{ whenever } s \in R^\ell(\sigma^*), s' \notin R^\ell(\sigma^*) \right\},$$

$$R_i^{k+1}(\sigma^*) = \left\{ s_i \mid \exists \{\sigma^n\} \rightarrow \sigma \in F^k(\sigma^*) \text{ satisfying the above conditions with } s_i \text{ a best reply to } \sigma_{-i}^n \text{ for all } n \right\},$$

$$R^{k+1}(\sigma^*) = \prod_i R_i^{k+1}(\sigma^*).$$

Any $\sigma \in F^k(\sigma^*)$ is a k th-order forward induction equilibrium.

We next show how the certifier's choice restricts the investors' belief and determines their unique relevant strategy. Consider Σ^* that contains the sequential equilibrium induced by $(\bar{c}, \underline{\tau}(\bar{c}), P(\emptyset)(\underline{\tau}(\bar{c})))$.³⁰ Let $\{\sigma^n\}$ be any sequence of ε -perfect equilibria converging to some $\sigma \in \Sigma^*$ with $\sigma_C^n(\bar{c}) \rightarrow 1$. In each σ^n , every player's strategy is a best reply to the sequence. Let α_n denote investors' posterior under σ^n . We claim that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n \geq \frac{\bar{V}(c_2) - \bar{V}(\bar{c})}{\underline{V}(\bar{c}) - \bar{V}(\bar{c})}$. Suppose not. Then for all large n , the certifier's payoff from choosing \bar{c} is strictly less than the payoff guarantee of $\bar{V}(c_2)$,

³⁰Formally, the strategy profile should prescribe play at each information set. We omit the specification of part of the strategy for simplicity if no confusion arises.

implying that \bar{c} cannot be a best reply in σ_n . It follows that $\alpha \equiv \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n \geq \frac{\bar{V}(c_2) - \bar{V}(\bar{c})}{\underline{V}(\bar{c}) - \bar{V}(\bar{c})} > 0$. In the pure strategy equilibrium, investors thus have a unique best reply $P(\emptyset)(\underline{\tau}(\bar{c}))$ conditional on non-disclosure, i.e., $P(\emptyset)(\underline{\tau}(\bar{c})) \in R_I^1(\sigma)$ and $\frac{\sigma_I^n(P(\emptyset)(\bar{\tau}(\bar{c})))}{\sigma_I^n(P(\emptyset)(\underline{\tau}(\bar{c})))} \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

To be second-order relevant for $\Sigma^*(\sigma)$, the firm's choice of the threshold must be a best reply along some ε -perfect sequence $\{\tilde{\sigma}^n\} \rightarrow \tilde{\sigma} \in F^1(\Sigma^*)$ that respects the first-order relevance for R^1 . Because investors choose $P(\emptyset)(\underline{\tau}(\bar{c}))$ with probability 1 in the limit, no ε -perfect sequence in $F^1(\Sigma^*)$ can make $\bar{\tau}(\bar{c})$ a best reply, as the firm has a strict incentive to disclose above $\underline{\tau}(\bar{c})$. Hence, choosing $\bar{\tau}(\bar{c})$ as the threshold is deleted by the second-order forward induction.

Anticipating that the firm will choose $\underline{\tau}(\bar{c})$, the certifier's optimal fee is \bar{c} by Lemma 4 in the unique forward induction equilibrium. \square

Additional Proofs from Section 5

In what follows, we assume that the assumptions in Proposition 5 hold. Lemma 10 shows that the equilibrium disclosure strategy features a threshold.

Lemma 10. *Suppose that \tilde{v} has continuous strictly positive density on $[\underline{v}, \bar{v}]$, and $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ is independent of \tilde{v} with a continuous strictly positive log-concave density on \mathbb{R} . For any $\tau \in [\underline{v}, \bar{v}]$, (i) $P(x)$ is increasing in x ; (ii) $\mathbb{E}(P(\tilde{x})|v)$ is increasing in v ; (iii) the firm's disclosure strategy features a threshold in equilibrium; (iv) $\mathbb{E}(P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})|\tau)$ is increasing and continuous in τ .*

Proof of Lemma 10. Because f_ε is log-concave, $f(x|v) = f_\varepsilon(x-v)$ satisfies MLRP. Equivalently, for any $x_2 > x_1$, $f_\varepsilon(x_2 - v)/f_\varepsilon(x_1 - v)$ is increasing in v . Hence, the posterior distribution of v conditional on disclosure and x is ordered by monotone likelihood ratio as x rises. So the posterior mean $P(x) = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} \geq \tau, x]$ is increasing in x .

Now fix τ . For any $v_2 > v_1$, $\mathbb{E}(P(\tilde{x})|v_2) \geq \mathbb{E}(P(\tilde{x})|v_1)$, because $P(x)$ is increasing in x and $v_2 + \tilde{\varepsilon} \geq v_1 + \tilde{\varepsilon}$ pointwise. So $\mathbb{E}(P(\tilde{x})|v)$ is increasing in v .

Further because the non-disclosure price $P(\emptyset)$ does not depend on the firm's realized type v , the net gain from disclosing, $\mathbb{E}(P(\tilde{x})|v) - c - P(\emptyset)$, is increasing in v . So the set of types that

prefer disclosure is an upper interval, i.e. the best response is a threshold.

For the last part, if $\tau_2 > \tau_1$, then $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} \geq \tau_2, x] \geq \mathbb{E}[\tilde{v}|\tilde{v} \geq \tau_1, x]$ for all x . Because $P(x)$ is increasing in x and $\mathbb{E}(P(\tilde{x})|\nu)$ is increasing in ν , we have

$$\mathbb{E}(P(\tau_2 + \tilde{\varepsilon})|\tau_2) \geq \mathbb{E}(P(\tau_1 + \tilde{\varepsilon})|\tau_2) \geq \mathbb{E}(P(\tau_1 + \tilde{\varepsilon})|\tau_1).$$

So $\mathbb{E}(P(\tau + \tilde{\varepsilon})|\tau)$ is increasing in τ . Continuity follows from dominated convergence and continuity of the posterior mean on compact support. \square

Define for simplicity $EP(\tau) \equiv \mathbb{E}(P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau)$. We make the following additional assumptions: (i) the pdf of ν , $f_\nu(\cdot)$ is logconcave, analytic at $\underline{\nu}$ and with $f_\nu(\bar{\nu}) = 0$, (ii) the pdf of ε , $f_\varepsilon(\cdot)$, is symmetric and logconcave. Hereafter, we denote $F_\nu(\cdot)$ (resp., $F_\varepsilon(\cdot)$) the cdf of ν (resp., ε). Lemma 11 is used to prove Proposition 5.

Lemma 11. $EP'(\underline{\nu}) < \frac{1}{2}$.

Proof of Lemma 11. Note that $EP'(\tau) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} P'(\tau + \varepsilon) f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon$. Define $s(\varepsilon) \equiv (\log f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon))'$ and $t(\nu) \equiv (\log f_\nu(\nu))'$.

Recall that:

$$P(x) = \frac{\int \nu f_\nu(\nu) f_\varepsilon(x - \nu) d\nu}{\int f_\nu(\nu) f_\varepsilon(x - \nu) d\nu},$$

so that denoting densities $\pi_x(\nu) \propto f_\nu(\nu) f_\varepsilon(x - \nu)$ and $\rho_x(\varepsilon) \propto f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) f_\nu(x - \varepsilon)$, standard covariance identities imply

$$P'(y) = \text{Cov}_{\pi_x}(\nu, s(x - \nu)), \quad r'(y) \equiv \frac{d}{dx}(x - P(x)) = \text{Cov}_{\rho_x}(\varepsilon, t(x - \varepsilon)).$$

Since f_ε, f_ν are logconcave, s' and t' are negative, so that $P'(x) \geq 0$ and $r'(x) \geq 0$, so $0 \leq P'(x) = 1 - r'(x) \leq 1$.

By symmetry of f_ε ,

$$EP'(\underline{v}) = \int_0^\infty f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) (P'(\underline{v} + \varepsilon) + P'(\underline{v} - \varepsilon)) d\varepsilon.$$

Since $P(\cdot)$ is increasing,

$$\int_0^\infty P'(\underline{v} + \varepsilon) d\varepsilon \leq v - P(\underline{v}), \quad \int_0^\infty P'(\underline{v} - \varepsilon) d\varepsilon \leq P(\underline{v}) - \underline{v}.$$

Because f_ε is symmetric and log-concave, it is nonincreasing on $[0, \infty)$; by the rearrangement inequality, for any $h : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $\int_0^\infty h(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon \leq a$, $\int_0^\infty f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) h(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon \leq \int_0^a f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon$. Applying this to $h(\varepsilon) = P'(\underline{v} + \varepsilon)$ and $h(\varepsilon) = P'(\underline{v} - \varepsilon)$ yields

$$\int_0^\infty f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) P'(\underline{v} + \varepsilon) d\varepsilon \leq \int_0^{\bar{v} - P(\underline{v})} f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon, \quad \int_0^\infty f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) P'(\underline{v} - \varepsilon) d\varepsilon \leq \int_0^{P(\underline{v}) - \underline{v}} f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon.$$

It then follows that:

$$F_\varepsilon(P(\underline{v}) - \underline{v}) + F_\varepsilon(\bar{v} - P(\underline{v})) \leq F_\varepsilon(\bar{v} - \underline{v})$$

and therefore

$$EP'(\underline{v}) \leq F_\varepsilon(\bar{v} - \underline{v}) = \int_0^{\bar{v} - \underline{v}} f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon < \int_0^\infty f_\varepsilon(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2}.$$

□

Proposition 16. *There exists a non-empty set of costs with at least two subgame equilibria, i.e., $c_0 < \min(\psi(\underline{v}), \psi(\bar{v}))$.*

Proof of Proposition 16. We need to show that $\psi(\bar{v}) = \bar{v} - \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v})$, and $\psi(\underline{v}) = \mathbb{E}P(\underline{v} + \tilde{\varepsilon}) - \underline{v}$ are not a minimum of $\psi(\tau)$, and therefore $c_0 < \min(\psi(\underline{v}), \psi(\bar{v}))$.

First, we show that $\psi'(\underline{v}) > 0$. Under the assumption that $f_v(\cdot)$ is analytic at \underline{v} , there exists

$\zeta \geq 0$ such that $f_v(v) \sim k(v - \underline{v})^\zeta$, implying that

$$\frac{\partial P(\emptyset)}{\partial \tau} \sim \frac{f_v(\tau)}{F_v(\tau)}(\tau - P(\emptyset)) \sim \frac{\zeta + 1}{\zeta + 2} \geq \frac{1}{2}.$$

We know from lemma 11 that $EP'(\underline{\tau}) < 1/2$, which establishes the claim.

Second,

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \bar{v}} \frac{\partial P(\emptyset)}{\partial \tau} = f_v(\bar{v}) (\bar{v} - \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v})) = 0,$$

while because $P'(x) > 0$, it must hold that $EP'(\bar{\tau}) > 0$, as it is a non-degenerate expectation over all realizations of $P'(\cdot)$. This establishes the claim that $\psi'(\bar{v}) > 0$.

It then follows from these observations that $\psi(\cdot)$ is minimized on (\underline{v}, \bar{v}) , which implies from proposition 5 that the region with multiple equilibria $c \in (c_0, \min(\psi(\underline{v}), \psi(\bar{v})))$ is non-empty. \square

Proposition 16 can be further strengthened under unbounded support to show that, for any $c > c_0$, the model has at least two equilibria (even without normal distributions). To show this, we do not need logconcavity or symmetry but v to have regular priors, in the sense of, for $\tau \rightarrow -\infty$, $P(\emptyset) = \tau + o(\tau)$ and $E(v|\tau)/\tau$ converges to a number bounded away from one (both conditions are satisfied for almost all families of Bayesian updates). Then, $\psi(\tau) \rightarrow \infty$ and, since, at the upper tail, $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \psi(\tau) = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} EP(\tau) - \mathbb{E}(v) = \infty$, it must be that $\psi(\tau)$ has an interior minimum and, for any $c > c_0$, $\psi(\tau) - c$ has a root at each side of $\tau(c_0)$.

The next proposition specializes the analysis to truncated normals.

Proposition 17. *Suppose that \tilde{v} is a normally distributed random variable $N(0, \sigma)$ truncated at η .*

There exist three cost levels $c_0^l \leq c_0^m \leq c_0^h$, satisfying:

- (i) *if $c < c_0^l$, there is a unique subgame equilibrium and it must be full disclosure, i.e., $\tau(c) = \eta$;*
- (ii) *if $c_0^l \leq c \leq c_0^m$, there can be one or more subgame equilibria and at least one features partial disclosure for $c \in (c_0^l, c_0^m]$;*
- (iii) *if $c \in (c_0^m, c_0^h]$, there exist at least two subgame equilibria with finite thresholds such that the highest equilibrium threshold $\bar{\tau}(c)$ is increasing in c ;*

(iv) if $c > c_0^h$, there is a unique subgame equilibrium $\bar{\tau}(c)$.

Further, if η is sufficiently small (large), $c_0^l \leq c_0^m < c_0^h$ (resp., $c_0^l = c_0^h$).

Lemma 12. Let ϕ and Φ denote the standard normal pdf and cdf. For

$$P(\emptyset; \tau) = \sigma \frac{\phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma}) - \phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})}{\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})}, \quad \text{where } \tau \geq \eta,$$

if $\eta \geq 0$, then

$$0 < \frac{d}{d\tau} P(\emptyset; \tau) \leq \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{for all } \tau \geq \eta,$$

with equality $\frac{1}{2}$ attained only in the right-limit $\tau \downarrow \eta$.

Proof of Lemma 12. Differentiating $P(\emptyset)$ with respect to τ gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dP(\emptyset)}{d\tau} &= \frac{\phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) \left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma} (\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})) - (\phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma}) - \phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})) \right)}{(\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma}))^2} \\ \frac{d^2}{d\tau^2} P(\emptyset) &= \frac{d}{d\tau} \left(\frac{\phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) \frac{\tau}{\sigma}}{\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})} - \frac{\phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) (\phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma}) - \phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}))}{(\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma}))^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{\phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})}{\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})} \left(1 - \left(\frac{\tau}{\sigma} + 2 \frac{\phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})}{\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})} \right) \left(\frac{\frac{\tau}{\sigma} (\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})) - (\phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma}) - \phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}))}{\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})} \right) \right) \\ &= - \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{\phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma})}{(\Phi(\frac{\tau}{\sigma}) - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma}))^3} \left(\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} \phi(w) dw \int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} (\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w)^2 \phi(w) dw - \left(\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} (\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w) \phi(w) dw \right)^2 \right). \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

We show that $\frac{d^2}{d\tau^2} P(\emptyset) < 0$ for all $\tau > \eta \geq 0$. Then $\frac{d}{d\tau} P(\emptyset)$ is strictly decreasing on $[\eta, \infty)$.

Because $\lim_{\tau \downarrow \eta} \frac{d}{d\tau} P(\emptyset) = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d}{d\tau} P(\emptyset) = 0$, monotonicity implies that $0 < \frac{d}{d\tau} P(\emptyset) < \frac{1}{2}$

for $\tau > \eta \geq 0$.

Consider the probability measure on $[\frac{\eta}{\sigma}, \frac{\tau}{\sigma}]$ with density $d\mu(w) := \left(\phi(w) / \left(\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} \phi(w) dw \right) \right) dw$.

Under μ ,

$$\frac{\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} (\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w) \phi(w) dw}{\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} \phi(w) dw} = \mathbb{E}_{\mu}[\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w], \quad \frac{\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} (\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w)^2 \phi(w) dw}{\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} \phi(w) dw} = \mathbb{E}_{\mu}[(\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w)^2].$$

Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} \phi(w) dw \int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} (\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w)^2 \phi(w) dw - \left(\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} (\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w) \phi(w) dw \right)^2 \\ &= \left(\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} \phi(w) dw \right)^2 \left(\mathbb{E}_{\mu}[(\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w)^2] - \mathbb{E}_{\mu}[\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w]^2 \right) \\ &= \left(\int_{\frac{\eta}{\sigma}}^{\frac{\tau}{\sigma}} \phi(w) dw \right)^2 \text{Var}_{\mu}(\frac{\tau}{\sigma} - w) \\ &\geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

and the inequality is strict whenever $\tau > \eta$. Therefore, $\frac{d^2}{d\tau^2} P(\emptyset) < 0$ for all $\tau > \eta \geq 0$ by (37) and $\frac{d}{d\tau} P(\emptyset)$ is strictly decreasing on $[\eta, \infty)$. \square

Proof of Proposition 17. For any $\tau \geq \eta$, it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(\tilde{v} | \tilde{v} \in [\eta, \tau]) &\leq \tau = \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} \tau + \frac{s\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{\tau s/\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} - \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \tilde{Y}\right] \\ &< \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} \tau + \frac{s\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \lambda\left(\mathbb{E}\left[\frac{\tau s/\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} - \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \tilde{Y}\right]\right) \\ &\leq \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} \tau + \frac{s\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \mathbb{E}\left[\lambda\left(\frac{\tau s/\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} - \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \tilde{Y}\right)\right] = \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau]. \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from $\lambda(z)$ strictly increasing in z , and the third inequality follows from $\lambda(z)$ strictly convex in z and the Jensen's inequality. It follows from continuity that there is a unique subgame equilibrium that features full disclosure (i.e., $\tau(c) = \eta$) when c is sufficiently small. This proves part (i).

Recall that $\Delta(\tau; c) = \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon) | \tau] - c - P(\emptyset)$. Note that $\partial\Delta(\tau; c)/\partial\tau$ is independent of c .

So we write it as $\Delta'(\tau)$ for short. Let $\mathcal{N} \equiv \{\tau \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau) < 0\}$. If $\mathcal{N} = \emptyset$, $\Delta'(\tau) \geq 0$ for all $\tau \geq \eta$. Either $\Delta' \equiv 0$ on the whole interval $[\eta, \infty)$ or it is positive almost everywhere. Further because $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Delta'(\tau) = a + (1 - a) - 0 = 1$, $\Delta(\tau; c)$ is strictly increasing in τ . So $\Delta(\tau; c) = 0$ at most once.

If $c < \mathbb{E}[P(\eta + \varepsilon)|\eta] - \eta$, then $\Delta(\tau; c) = \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c - P(\emptyset) \geq \mathbb{E}[P(\eta + \varepsilon)|\eta] - c - \eta > 0$ for any $\tau \geq \eta$, the unique equilibrium features full disclosure.

If $c \geq \mathbb{E}[P(\eta + \varepsilon)|\eta] - \eta$, there exists τ' such that $\Delta(\tau'; c) = 0$ by continuity of Δ . Moreover, $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau]$ is strictly convex in τ . So $\partial \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau]/\partial \tau$ is strictly increasing in τ . Further, because $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \partial \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau]/\partial \tau = 1$, there is $\tau'' \geq 0$ sufficiently large such that $\partial \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau]/\partial \tau \geq 3/4$ for all $\tau \geq \tau''$. Let $\bar{\eta} \equiv \tau''$. For any $\eta \geq \bar{\eta} \geq 0$ and any $\tau \geq \eta$, we have $dP(\emptyset)(\tau)/d\tau \leq 1/2$ by lemma 12. Then

$$\Delta'(\tau) = \frac{\partial \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - P(\emptyset)}{\partial \tau} \geq \frac{3}{4} - \frac{1}{2} > 0,$$

implying that Δ is strictly increasing in τ for any $\tau \geq \eta$. Hence, there is a unique subgame equilibrium $\bar{\tau}(c)$ if $\eta \geq \bar{\eta}$ and $c \geq \mathbb{E}[P(\eta + \varepsilon)|\eta] - \eta$. This proves part (iv) when $c_0^l = c_0^h$.

Next, consider $\mathcal{N} \neq \emptyset$. By the intermediate value theorem, there exists at least one local minimizer τ^* such that $\Delta'(\tau^*) = 0$ and $\Delta''(\tau^*) > 0$. In other words, the set $\{\tau \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau) = 0, \Delta''(\tau) > 0\}$ is not empty. Let $c_0^l \equiv \inf_{\tau \geq \eta} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - P(\emptyset)(\tau)$. If $c < c_0^l$, then $\Delta(\tau; c) = \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c - P(\emptyset) > 0$ for all $\tau \geq \eta$. Then the unique equilibrium features full disclosure. If $c \geq c_0^l$, then there exists τ such that $\Delta(\tau; c) = \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c - P(\emptyset) \leq 0$. Further because as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] &= \frac{\sigma^2}{\sigma^2 + s^2} \tau + \frac{s\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \mathbb{E}[\lambda(\frac{\tau s/\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} - \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + s^2}} \tilde{Y})] \sim \tau \rightarrow \infty \\ P(\emptyset) &\rightarrow \sigma \frac{\phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})}{1 - \Phi(\frac{\eta}{\sigma})} \text{ which is a finite constant,} \end{aligned}$$

it must be that $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Delta(\tau; c) > 0$. So there is at least one subgame equilibrium with a finite

threshold. When $c > c_0^l$, we claim that there is at least one subgame equilibrium that features partial disclosure. It follows from $c > c_0^l$ that

$$\inf_{\tau \geq \eta} (\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c - P(\emptyset)(\tau)) = \inf_{\tau \geq \eta} (\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - P(\emptyset)(\tau)) - c = c_0^l - c < 0.$$

So there exists some $\tau \geq \eta$ such that $\Delta(\tau) < 0$. Hence, there must be a partial disclosure equilibrium by the Intermediate value theorem. This proves part (ii).

Let $c_0^m \equiv \sup_{\tau \geq \eta} \{\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - P(\emptyset)(\tau) : \Delta'(\tau) = 0, \Delta''(\tau) > 0\}$ and $c_0^h \equiv \sup\{\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - P(\emptyset)(\tau) : \eta \leq \tau \leq \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}\}$. Let τ^* be the local minimizer such that $\Delta'(\tau) = 0$ and $\Delta''(\tau) > 0$, and maximizes $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - P(\emptyset)(\tau)$ among all local minimizers. Then $\Delta(\tau^*; c_0^m) = \mathbb{E}[P(\tau^* + \varepsilon)|\tau^*] - c_0^m - P(\emptyset)(\tau^*) = 0$. So for $c > c_0^m$, there exists a local minimizer τ^* such that $\Delta(\tau^*; c) < 0$.

We show that there are two solutions to $\Delta(\tau; c) = 0$ that straddle τ^* if $c \leq c_0^h$. By the definition of c_0^h , if $c \leq c_0^h$, there is $\tau \in [\eta, \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}]$ such that $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c - P(\emptyset)(\tau) \geq 0$. Otherwise there is $c' < c \leq c_0^h$ such that $\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - P(\emptyset)(\tau) \leq c'$ for all τ in the compact interval $[\eta, \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}]$, contradicting the definition of the supremum. By the Intermediate value theorem, there is some $\tau_1 \in [\eta, \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}]$ such that $\Delta(\tau_1; c) = 0$, since $\Delta(\tau^*; c) < 0$. Furthermore, when $c > c_0^m$ and $\tau = \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}$, $\Delta(\tau; c) = \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c - P(\emptyset)(\tau) < \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c_0^m - P(\emptyset)(\tau) \leq \sup_{\tau \geq \eta} \{\mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - P(\emptyset)(\tau) : \Delta'(\tau) = 0, \Delta''(\tau) > 0\} - c_0^m = 0$. Because $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Delta(\tau; c) > 0$, there is some $\tau_2 > \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}$ such that $\Delta(\tau_2; c) = 0$. Hence, there exist at least two subgame equilibria with finite thresholds. The highest threshold satisfies $\Delta''(\tau) > 0$. It follows from $\partial\Delta(\tau; c)/\partial c = -1$ and the Implicit function theorem that the highest equilibrium threshold $\bar{\tau}(c)$ increases with c . This proves part (iii).

If $c > c_0^h$, for all $\tau \in [\eta, \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}]$, $\Delta(\tau; c) = \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c - P(\emptyset)(\tau) < \mathbb{E}[P(\tau + \varepsilon)|\tau] - c_0^h - P(\emptyset)(\tau) \leq 0$ by the definition of c_0^h . Because $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \Delta(\tau; c) = \infty$ and there is no local minimizer for $\tau > \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}$, $\Delta(\tau; c)$ is increasing

in τ for $\tau > \max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}$. Further there is a unique solution τ to $\Delta(\tau; c) = 0$ (and this solution is greater than $\max\{\tau' \geq \eta : \Delta'(\tau') = 0, \Delta''(\tau') > 0\}$). This proves part (iv). \square

The proposition below illustrates the role of boundedness. The lower-tail truncation changes the model only through the non-disclosure price, and this change becomes arbitrarily small on any fixed range of thresholds as the lower bound moves far enough into the left tail. Hence the main force behind Proposition 1 survives: over an intermediate range of fees, the lower threshold decreases with c . What bounded support changes is the behavior at the tail. Once the threshold approaches the lower bound, non-disclosure cannot be made arbitrarily punitive. So the mechanism eventually shuts down and, for sufficiently high fees, the unique equilibrium is no disclosure.

Proposition 18. *Fix a compact interval of fees I on which the unbounded model has equilibria $\underline{\tau}(c)$ and $\bar{\tau}(c)$. For η sufficiently negative, the truncated normal model has equilibria $\underline{\tau}_\eta(c)$ and $\bar{\tau}_\eta(c)$ on I , and*

$$\sup_{c \in I} |\underline{\tau}_\eta(c) - \underline{\tau}(c)| \rightarrow 0, \quad \sup_{c \in I} |\bar{\tau}_\eta(c) - \bar{\tau}(c)| \rightarrow 0.$$

Lemma 13. *Let $\psi_\eta(\tau)$ be the marginal disclosure benefit at the threshold under a truncated normal distribution with lower truncation at η , and $\psi(\tau)$ be the the marginal disclosure benefit in the unbounded normal model. For every compact interval $K \subset \mathbb{R}$,*

$$\sup_{\tau \in K} |\psi_\eta(\tau) - \psi(\tau)| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \eta \rightarrow -\infty.$$

Proof of Lemma 13. Under the truncated normal distribution, the expected price conditional on disclosure is unchanged, because lower truncation does not affect the conditional distribution given $v \geq \tau$. So the only term that changes is the non-disclosure price $P(\emptyset)$. Recall that $P_\eta(\emptyset) = \sigma \frac{\phi(\eta/\sigma) - \phi(\tau/\sigma)}{\Phi(\tau/\sigma) - \Phi(\eta/\sigma)}$. As $\eta \rightarrow -\infty$, both $\phi(\eta/\sigma)$ and $\Phi(\eta/\sigma)$ converge to zero. Hence, for each fixed τ ,

$$P_\eta(\emptyset) \rightarrow -\sigma \frac{\phi(\tau/\sigma)}{\Phi(\tau/\sigma)} = P(\emptyset),$$

where $P(\emptyset)$ is the non-disclosure price in the unbounded model. Furthermore, because K is compact, the denominator $\Phi(\tau/\sigma)$ is bounded away from zero on K . Therefore, the convergence is uniform on K and $\sup_{\tau \in K} |\psi_\eta(\tau) - \psi(\tau)| \rightarrow 0$. \square

Proof of Proposition 18. Because ψ_η is uniformly close to ψ on K by Lemma 13, $\psi_\eta(\tau) = c$ has solutions $\underline{\tau}_\eta(c)$ and $\bar{\tau}_\eta(c)$ close to the baseline thresholds for all $c \in I$, provided that η is sufficiently negative. The uniform closeness gives the stated convergence on any compact range of fees. \square

So a sufficiently low lower bound reproduces the unbounded behavior arbitrarily well.